

NEANIAS

Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges

Deliverable

**Deliverable: Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater
Thematic Services #1**

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 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

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Authors (s)	Josep Quintana (Coronis); Ricard Campos (Coronis); Paraskevi Nomikou (NKUA), Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA), Kalliopi Baika (AMU); Jafar Anbar (AMU); Jean-Christophe Sourisseau (AMU) Danai Lampridou (NKUA); Makis Ntouskos (NTUA); Vasilios Tsironis (NKUA); Panagiotis Mertikas (NKUA); Nikolaos Foskolos (Teledyne); Paul Wintersteller (Teledyne)		
Contributor (s)	Eva Sciacca (INAF)		
Reviewer(s)	Fulvio Galeazzi (GAAR)		
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Abstract

This document reports on the 1st release of the underwater services and the software underlying each service. This report, NEANIAS deliverable 2.4, is published right after the first thematic underwater services release, i.e., deliverable D2.3 and the initial validation phase based on mostly internal end-users.

The U1 [UW_BAT] “Bathymetry mapping from acoustic data service implementation” provides an advanced user-friendly, cloud-based version of the popular MB-System software, for processing bathymetric data through Jupyter Notebooks. The U2 [UW_MOS] service “Seafloor Mosaicking from Optical Data” delivers 2D/3D mosaics produced by a set of images and navigational data. The expected output is achieved by a processing pipeline based on in-house solutions and open-source libraries. Finally, the U3 [UW_MAP] service “Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data” provides an easy-to-use, cloud-based solution incorporating machine learning frameworks in order to identify different seabed classes.

For each *released* service a point-of-access is provided, as well as the relevant documentation, which is organized under NEANIAS docs service at <https://docs.neanias.eu/en/latest>.

Services reported here have gone through the first release round, most services have been integrated to NEANIAS authentication system service, the documentation workflow, and integrated with GARR infrastructure services. As expected, this first services milestone uncovered some gaps in the services deployment stack and integration with other core and delivery services will be addressed for the next milestones and releases.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

The WP2 “Underwater Services” involves three out of nine thematic services of the NEANIAS project (<https://www.neanias.eu/>). The overall common goal is the development of thematic cloud services which support the analysis and data management of a large diversity of tasks within the fields of underwater, atmosphere and space research, development and. Easy to handle, fair to use and platform independent.

1.2. Content and rationale

This deliverable, D2.4, is a report containing the details of the developed and validated Underwater Services, delivered in the 1st release listed in the deliverable D2.3 “Underwater Thematic Services Release #1 (U1/U2/U3)” [2].

Preliminary documents have been prepared for each of the services (U1, U2, U3), within the NEANIAS WP2 workspace¹, collecting the required datasets for service validation, software underlying technologies as well as collecting all possible contributions as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to evaluate their success.

The document reports, for each of the underwater service, the main release components as identified in WP7 for their delivery and assessment [5,6]; and their integration with core services provided by WP6 [3,4]. Moreover, service *documentation* and service *interface(s)* exposing their functionalities in a customized way are reported and mainly provided by URLs. Furthermore, Service Validation as well as addressed User Requirements, identified and reported in D4.1, guiding the development are described. NEANIAS Underwater services are built on top of TRL6 software – software fully functional in their original domain – and evolve towards TRL8 – in our context, fully operational in a cloud environment. This first release aims at deploying the software in the context of the NEANIAS infrastructure, using cloud infrastructure and services provided by GARR, and integrate relevant documentation, to be used as a test run for uncovering major obstacles across the NEANIAS collaboration. In the first release an initial set of selected features are functional and stable, and documentation is complete enough to cover them, thus rendering the service usable by end users.

Progress towards TRL8 (cloud complete operation and stabilization) will be described in upcoming deliverables/milestones.

¹ NEANIAS WP2 Documentation (internal access only): <https://citegr.sharepoint.com/teams/h2020-neanias/Shared%20Documents/Forms/AllItems.aspx?viewid=a9894888%2D0c1a%2D427a%2D8a45%2Ddd2ce3ffb32c&id=%2Fteams%2Fh2020%2Dneanias%2FShared%20Documents%2FWP02%2DUnderwater>

1.3. Structure of the document

This document consists of 5 chapters. Chapter 2 covers the general release overview of the Underwater thematic services with respect to their usage, deployment and the projects timeline. Chapter 3 provides all the information of the thematic services such as the status, endpoint, and documentation up until the delivery of the present document. Chapter 4 reports about the validation of the services as well as the user requirements fulfilment. Finally, chapter 5 encapsulates the attainment of the objectives, raised issues to be tackled and future steps.

2. Release overview

2.1. Underwater Services overview

The three NEANIAS Underwater services aim to support bathymetric, photogrammetric and seafloor backscatter processing and analysis to enhance a toolbox for a broad underwater community. All services got nice logos which are shown in figure 1. Acknowledgement of our gratitude goes to *Dora Giannopoulou (ATHENA)*. A brief overview of the services is given below. Further information and links to documentation of the services can be found in chapter 3 of this document.

Figure 1: The NEANIAS underwater logos

The **UW-BAT** (Bathyprocessing) service provides a large number of tools to post-process vendor specific raw data. Its approach is to create digital terrain models (DTM) and maps from multibeam echosounder (MBES) raw data. In the final release a hydroacoustic workflow, realized within Jupyter Lab/Notebooks, guides the user through several steps of filtering/cleaning or offset and lever arm as well as tide, draft or sound velocity corrections. At all times the user can additionally utilize an extensive toolbox for special purposes on the given terminal or in separate Notebooks. The service should encourage people from other fields e.g. archaeologist, geoscientists or engineers to dig into the world of bathymetry and seafloor backscatter processing. The service is accessible through the following link: <http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu>.

The **UW-MOS** service, deals with optical mapping in underwater environments. It provides a set of sub services related to mapping using images, including camera calibration, image quality check, 2D mosaicing and 3D reconstruction. The camera calibration allows obtaining the intrinsic parameters ruling the image projection

process, a piece of information that can be used to improve both 2D and 3D mapping. Also, prior to the use of the data within mapping, the service provides a pre-check of the data quality, so that the user is aware of the less informative images in their datasets. Finally, the user can upload the images and construct a map of the observed area. Depending on the properties of the scene observed by the camera at the time of capturing the images, the user can select to reconstruct a 2D or a 3D map. The service is accessible through <https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>.

The **UW-MAP** Seabed Classification from Multispectral, Multibeam Data service delivers a user-friendly cloud-based solution integrating cutting-edge machine learning frameworks for mapping several seabed classes. The service focuses on the exploitation of recent cutting-edge multibeam echosounders which collect backscatter data at multiple spectral frequencies offering capabilities for systematic and accurate mapping of the seabed. The main service novelty lies in serving unified classification models trained considering different seabed categories. The validation process is performed considering a diverse selection of multispectral multibeam datasets. The service is accessible through the following link: <https://uw-map.neanias.eu/>.

2.2. Release of the Underwater & Co-designed Core Services

The first release of the thematic services targets the NEANIAS ecosystem, currently realized on cloud infrastructures provided by GARR (<https://cloud.garr.it/>) All documentation related to the Underwater, and NEANIAS services in common, is powered by the Read the Docs service (<https://readthedocs.org/>) and has been delivered to the NEANIAS documentation repository at <https://docs.neanias.eu>. The relevant source code is handled by the NEANIAS GitLab repository (<https://gitlab.neanias.eu/>) while some parts are hosted in other repositories including <https://www.gitlab.com> and <https://www.github.com>. Additionally, container images used for deploying the services are hosted in the NEANIAS container registry.

The underwater services and their integration with core services for authentication and authorization (WP6 & WP7 [3,4,5]), as well as with services for access to computational and data resources, are deployed on either the GARR OpenStack (<https://cloud.garr.it/support/kb/openstack/>) instances and/or on the GARR Kubernetes (<https://cloud.garr.it/support/kb/kubernetes/>) cluster for load scalability.

The NEANIAS Data Sharing Service (DaShaS) (part of core service C2) has also been employed for allowing the end users to upload and share their data with services for processing, and for allowing the services to store and share to the users results and other relevant files.

Another potentially relevant core service in the underwater context would be VD-Maps, being developed under WP6. Services described in this deliverable will, at a later stage, be updated to exploit the functionalities provided by VD-Maps. Since Coronis is the

main developer of both the UW-MOS service within this WP and the VD-Maps core service, they will lead the integration of this service (starting with UW-MOS), and they will also offer support for other services within this WP willing to adhere to this core service.

2.3. Releases timeline

The Underwater Thematic services are released in three main cycles, as shown in table 1. Release #1 has been delivered in M12 (Deliverable D2.3 [2] and the relevant report in this document). Table 2 below summarizes the Underwater services released and the main information related to the release.

Deliverable	Release	Production	Testing	Pre-release	Production	Testing	Pre-release
D2.3	#1	12	11	10	31/10/20	30/09/20	31/08/20
D2.5	#2	23	22	21	30/09/21	31/08/21	31/07/21
D2.7	#3	30	29	28	30/04/22	31/03/22	28/02/22

Table 1: Software development plan of the Underwater thematic services releases including estimated dates for pre-releases, testing and production. Production, Testing and Prerelease show months from start of project

Detailed plans for the 2nd release are reported in the next section for each Underwater service.

Table 2: Second iteration of software release

Short name	Sector ¹	Lead ²	TRL ³	Version ⁴	Core Integration ⁵	Documentation Status ⁶	Testing Status ⁷	EOSC Reg. Status ⁸
UW-BAT	Underwater	TELEDYNE	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI in progress	In progress	In progress	no
UW-MOS	Underwater	CORONIS	TRL7	1.0.0	AAI	complete	In progress	no
UW-MAP	Underwater	ATHENA	TRL7	1.0.2	AAI	complete	in progress	no

3. Underwater Thematic Services

This chapter provides a tabular overview of each service: status, its endpoints, and links to further information.

3.1. U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data (UW-BAT)

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
UW-BAT	TELEDYNE	UBREMEN All WP2 partners evaluating the current service release

Service Status	The U1 service has been released in its first version v1.0.0 being deployed and spawned through the Kubernetes Cluster on the GARR Cloud. The integrated NEANIAS AAI core service allows access through the NEANIAS SSO. JupyterLab provides the user a simplified access to the command-line driven program package MB-System and its dependencies.
Service Endpoints	Service: http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u1-bathyprocessing/en/latest/index.html
Software information	The UW-BAT Bathyprocessing docker image and code: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/u1-service/bathyprocessing https://gitlab.neanias.eu/nikolaos.foskolos/bathy-processing The MB-System project: https://www.mbari.org/products/research-software/mb-system/ The MB-System Cookbook: http://www3.mbari.org/products/mbsystem/mb-cookbook/index.html
Plans for 2nd release	Data management – include the NEANIAS NextCloud service Jupyter Notebook – prepare workflows for several processing scenarios (e.g. MBES recorded from vessel or AUV) OTPS – implement tide correction by providing the OTPS database in a separate, permanent storage accessible through all deployed U1 services GMT – resolve current gmt.conf issues Other – add further core services e.g. logging, accounting

3.2. U2 – Seafloor Mosaicking from Optical Data (UW-MOS)

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
UW-MOS	CORONIS	All WP2 partners evaluating the current service release

Service Status	<p>UW-MOS is running in production environment at GARR cloud, and provides four sub-services/tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibrate a camera. • Check image data quality. • Create a 2D image mosaic. • Create a 3D model. <p>The user can launch more than a task at the same time.</p> <p>Demo data for each task is available in its corresponding “Demo” section in the documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service</p>
Service Endpoints	<p>Service: https://uw-mos.neanias.eu</p> <p>Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service</p>
Software information	<p>Source code divided in 4 repositories at Neanias’ GitLab:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main app: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/u2_service/u2_app • Tasks (depends on internal code/projects from Coronis): https://gitlab.neanias.eu/u2_service/u2_tasks • Docker compose: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/u2_service/u2_compose • Documentation: https://gitlab.neanias.eu/u2_service/u2_docs
Plans for 2nd release	<p>Connect camera calibration with other tasks to use its results as input for the 2D image mosaicking and the 3D modelling tasks.</p> <p>Add more parameters for each service.</p> <p>Provide options for image enhancement e.g. improve images with low data quality.</p> <p>Improve presentation of results to the user.</p> <p>Add the NEANIAS common User Interface (UI) to the service.</p> <p>Add other core services: logging, accounting, etc.</p> <p>Data management: interface to NEANIAS Data Sharing Service.</p>

3.3. U3 – Seabed Classification from Multispectral Multibeam Data (UW-MAP)

Short name	Lead partner	Contributors
UW-MAP	ATHENA	NKUA, All WP2 partners evaluating the current service release

Service Status	UW-MAP serves trained models for classifying different seabed types (e.g. mud, mud sand, sand, gravel, etc.) from multispectral multibeam (3-band) data. The service is deployed on the GARR infrastructure. User authentication and authorization is handled by the NEANIAS AAI service (C2- 2 nd group of core services). UW-MAP service makes use of the NEANIAS Data Sharing Service (C2) for providing demo and validation datasets.
Service Endpoints	Documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service Service: https://uw-map.neanias.eu
Software information	Source Code: https://gitlab.com/mdouskos/mapseabed (private) https://gitlab.com/neanias-services/mapseabed-server (private) https://gitlab.neanias.eu/u3-service/composefiles Current Release: 1.0.2
Plans for 2nd release	Improve functionality and usability based on user feedback by testing on various datasets. Integration with C4 (4 th group of core services) core services for enhanced visualization.

4. Underwater Services Validation and User Requirements fulfilment

In order to assess the user acceptance/validation of the provided functionalities, this chapter reports on the services access and conduction of each services workflow based on demo- or user-datasets. Furthermore, the fulfilled user requirements by each of the services are summarized.

4.1. U1 - Bathymetry Mapping from Acoustic Data (UW-BAT)

4.1.1. Service Usage

This chapter describes the current handling of the service in accordance to the given processing steps shown in the detailed technical online documentation (see link in chapter 3.1). The service allows hydroacoustic corrections of raw bathymetry data, given in different binary vendor formats utilizing MB-System [11] and depending software packages. A JupyterLab (Fig. 2) serves as the default frontend after logon through the AAI core service. Currently there are no pre-defined workflows created as Jupyter Notebooks. This forces the user of the 1st release to work with a number of terminal commands provided in the online documentation mentioned above. A further limitation of the release is due to deployment on the Kubernetes Cluster, which does not allow the forwarding for X11/Motif which in fact means that 3D manual editing like mbeditviz cannot be used in this version.

Figure 2: JupyterLab surface of the UW-BAT service

Several Unix based packages are combined to implement the service. MB-System, as the hydroacoustic/hydrography package utilizes e.g. the Generic Mapping Tools (GMT) to create the maps out of grids (digital terrain models/DTM) or backscatter mosaics (postscript/geotiff), while the “proj”-tool is used to correctly georeference the data in diverse projections. An example of how commands are released on a Notebook can be seen in figure 3 below.


```

%cd
lgmt defaults -D > ~/gmt.conf
lgmt set IO_NC4_CHUNK_SIZE=classic
lgmt set GMT_CUSTOM_LIBS /usr/local/lib/mbsystem.so
%cd work/
%pwd
  
```

Figure 3: Commands released end bloc in a single Notebook cell

Uploading data to the subdirectory work

This is a fairly easy task since JupyterLab offers drag and drop capability, as shown in the left window in fig. 2 & 3. Sample datasets can be downloaded via a link in the online documentation (see chapter 3).

Create a datalist, vessel-file & plot of the raw data

Just a view MB-System commands including their parametrisation released in a Notebook will allow to create a map of the raw data uploaded, within a very short time. The tools syntax and parametrisation are described in the online documentation (chapter 3.1 and in detail under the links given in step 4 below). Since these tools are indispensable for every kind of datasets processed we would briefly name them here: **mbm_makedatalist** allows to create a datalist which marks every survey line with a number, specific for the different vendor formats. The **mbmakeplatform** creates a so called vessel, containing all relevant information about lever-arms and offsets of the MBES used. The data is retrieved from the raw data headers. The program **mbpreprocess** creates several auxiliary files as well as the *.mbXX files. The later contain the raw data information 1:1 copied and in addition spaces to flag the datasets within the post-processing workflow. The Perl macro **mbm_makedatalist** creates the datalist further needed out of this *.mbXX files. At the end, the macro **mbm_plot** creates a cmd-script which finally produces the postscript map.

Currently the release of this script ends with an error with minor relevance but in order to be solved it highlights a nice feature of JupyterNotebook. In case something went wrong one can restart the kernel of the Notebook within a view seconds, by pressing the button shown in figure 4.

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```

essing@jupyter-paX  Untitled.ipynb
[ ] Code
!gmt set IO_NC4_CHUNK_SIZE 1000000
!gmt set GMT_CUSTOM_RENDERING_PATH /lib/mt
%cd work/
%pwd
  
```

Figure 4: JupyterLab – Restart the kernel

Display images in JupyterNotebook

We utilize GMT to convert the postscript into jpg images. Afterwards we point to the image which should be displayed. The next commands are to be released in a Notebooks cell.

```

!gmt ps2raster MAP-NAME.ps -A+n -Tj
or e.g. (!gmt psconvert MAP-NAME.ps -A+s5c -Tj)
from IPython.display import Image
Image(filename='MAP-NAME.jpg')
  
```

Results

Once the above-mentioned commands are released, the Notebook displays the generated postscript map converted as jpg (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: First results of a grid (DTM) drawn as hillshaded illuminated map.

Filter & correct bathymetry, create a map

This step contains vast possibilities of correcting, cleaning, filtering and processing of data. An initial set of pre- and post-processing options is described in the service documentation. The link to this documentation is shown in chapter 3.1 of this document. An overview of MB-Systems capabilities, tools and macros can be found here: http://www3.mbari.org/products/mbsystem/html/mbsystem_capabilities.html
The full range of options is given by the Unix man-pages documented under the link: http://www3.mbari.org/products/mbsystem/html/mbsystem_man_list.html

4.2. U2 - Seafloor Mosaicking from Optical Data (UW-MOS)

4.2.1. Overview of the Service

UW-MOS service, available at <https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>, is composed of four sub-services or *tasks*. Upon successful login, the different sub-services of UW-MOS are listed at the web page referenced above, namely:

- Calibrate a camera.
- Check image data quality.
- Create a 2D image mosaic.
- Create a 3D model.

Each of the services above will spawn a *task*. Each task is spawned asynchronously, so the user can start more than one task, and wait for their completion. For a more complete description of the service and its usage, and also links to sample data to test the services, please refer to the documentation page (<https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service>). Part of the sample data provided was extracted from [8].

4.2.2. Handling tasks

A user can spawn more than a task to be executed in parallel. The tasks spawned by the user are listed in the **Tasks** option at the menu bar (fig. 6). The different options depend on the task type, please refer to the documentation of each task for their description. Nonetheless, a common option of all tasks is the **Delete** option, represented by a red button, that deletes all user data on the server corresponding to the current task (both input images and results). The button **Update tasks status** assures one gets the current status even when leaving the tasks list open.

Figure 6: Handling Tasks on UW-MOS.

4.2.3. Task 1: camera calibration

This is the camera calibration task of UW-MOS, responsible for obtaining the intrinsic parameters ruling the internal geometry of the camera, i.e., how a point from the world is projected onto the image plane.

Calibration is usually performed using a calibration pattern, from which some points belonging to a common known plane can be extracted. The calibration method allows the user to use two different types of patterns: a chessboard pattern, with the common black/white squares, or a charuco pattern, an extension of the previous pattern, with the inclusion of easily-detectable AR markers, which help in the detection of the corners used for calibration.

The parameters to configure for this task are a set of images observing the calibration pattern and the parameters describing such patterns (fig. 7, see the documentation for more info). Upon task completion, the calibration will be in the form of a JSON file, which you can quickly view by clicking on the **See results** button, or download using the **Download** button. Moreover, the app allows downloading additional data showing the results of the calibration by clicking on the **Download Reprojection Data** button of the task item.

Camera Calibration

Select a set of calibration images:

17 files selected.

Choose the calibration pattern used:

Number of squares in X:

Number of squares in Y:

Squares' side length (m):

Markers' side length (m, only for Charuco patterns):

Dictionary ID (only for Charuco patterns):

Figure 7: Camera calibration configuration page.

4.2.4. Task 2: Check Image Data Quality

This task checks the quality and suitability of a set of images for 2D mosaicing and/or 3D reconstruction. The first step in both 2D mosaicing and 3D reconstruction tasks is to detect features on the images. These features are the base of the subsequent steps in both pipelines and, consequently, the input images must contain a relevant number of such features in order to obtain good results.

This task computes the number of AKAZE [9] features for each image of the input dataset. A minimum of 500 features is required to consider an image as suitable for mosaicing/reconstruction.

The usage of this service is quite simple, as it only requires the user to upload a set of images. Upon task completion, the **See the results** button on the task list will show a short report on the quality of the data, such as the one in fig 8.

Figure 8: Resulting image data quality report on the 2D dataset.

4.2.5. Task 3: Create a 2D Image Mosaic

This task constructs a 2D composite of all the input images (an *image mosaic*). This service assumes that the scene observed in the images is close to planar or, alternatively,

that the effects of parallax are negligible (e.g. a flyover of a downward-looking camera carried by an Autonomous Underwater Vehicle (AUV) surveying a given seabed area not having much 3D relief).

The current version of the service only requires the user to upload a set of images, which should have some overlap. The resulting mosaic is an image in PNG format. Upon task completion, the mosaic can be visualized directly on the browser (**See the results** button) or downloaded (**Download** button). The output expected from the sample dataset provided in the documentation is shown in fig 9.

Figure 9: Result of a 2D mosaicing task.

4.2.6. Task 4: Create a 3D Model

This task reconstructs a 3D scene observed in a set of overlapping images as a textured surface triangle mesh using [OpenMVG](#) and [OpenMVS](#) libraries.

The current version of the service only requires the user to upload a set of images. As in the 2D mosaicing case, images of the scene should have some overlap. However, the amount of overlap for 3D reconstruction should be larger: the more redundant the data is, the better. As a rule of thumb, consider that a part of the scene may be reconstructed only if it is seen, at least, in three different images from different point of views.

The output of this task is a 3D textured surface triangle mesh in the quite standard PLY format (<http://paulbourke.net/dataformats/ply/>), compatible with most common modelling/visualization programs (for example, <https://www.meshlab.net/>). The output expected from the sample dataset provided in the documentation is shown in fig. 10.

Figure 10: 3D reconstruction result.

4.3. U3 - UW-MAP Service Validation

The UW-MAP service produces a seabed classification map from Multispectral Multibeam Data. The User Interface of the service, shown after the user logs in, is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: UW-MAP service first release User Interface.

The service provides three seabed classification models which have been trained using a Random Forest classifier considering three, four and five different seabed classes, respectively. More details regarding how the classification models were obtained can be found in the relevant publication [7].

The users validated the service using the provided demo backscatter dataset, which corresponds to an area located at Patricia Bay, Canada, as well as two validation datasets which correspond to areas located at Bedford Basin (survey executed in 2017) and at Newbex, Portsmouth USA. These backscatter datasets, provided in GeoTIFF format, were obtained via suitable processing of the corresponding surveying data made available for the purposes of the 2017 R2Sonic Multispectral Multibeam Challenge. The demo and validation datasets are shown in Figure 12.

The validation tasks regarded the correct operation of the service as well as the qualitative evaluation of the classification maps produced by the service, in correspondence to the model selected by the user.

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Figure 12: Demo (Left Col.) and Validation (Mid & Right Col.) datasets with corresponding bathymetries (2nd row).

Regarding the evaluation of the produced maps, the service provided additional information regarding each target region to help the users assess the result quality. Specifically, geological maps of the regions corresponding to the Patricia (Demo) and Newbex (Validation) datasets were provided (Figures Figure 13 and Figure 14), while in the case of Bedford 2017 (Validation) datasets, the service provided the bathymetry of the area.

The validation summary section provides a comprehensive report of the users' feedback from the UW-MAP service validation.

Figure 15: UW-MAP service sample results. **Top Left:** Multispectral Trained Image, **Top Middle:** Classification Map 3 Classes, **Top Right:** Bathymetry of the area and at the bottom three representative images of each class

4.4. Validation

The first release of the underwater services (U1, U2, U3) was evaluated **against the initial set of requirements** that were collected by the end-users in the NEANIAS deliverable **D2.1** [3] (Chapter 3, Co-design and Service Specifications). Moreover, **almost 30 end-users** have used the services and reported their experience, evaluation and comments in the specific Test Logs (all attached in this deliverable in Appendix A). In particular, almost 10 end-users per service performed a number of executions with the demo or validation datasets in order to assess the overall performance and compare it against the initial requirements of D2.1.

Regarding the service assessment performed by the end-users, all NEANIAS internal end-users (in WP2) thoroughly evaluated the first release of all WP2 services. In particular, **NKUA, AMU and EUNICE** validated the three WP2 services and their comments and experience was marked down in specially prepared Test Log files (attached in the Appendix A).

Moreover, different **researchers and personnel**, from the internal end-users institutes/SMEs with **different background and expertise** evaluated the services in order to assess the services in terms of the **level** of experience, **technical or thematic** expertise required for using smoothly and operationally the deployed underwater services. Last but not least, based also on the specific application domain of each end-user more **emphasis** was given on specific services that are addressing domain-related challenges e.g., for EUNICE bathymetry mapping, AMU seafloor mosaicking.

Apart from the Test Log files, the following Table was prepared with the specific Requirement, Specification and Evaluation Outcomes of the 1st release.

Requirement				Specifications			1 st Release		
Req#	Requirement	Priority	Value	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Validated Status for U1	Validated Status for U2	Validated Status for U3
R00	Common AAI	High	High	S00	Common SSO Login for all NEANIAS services	U1, U2, U3	✓	✓	✓
R01	Upload, store and possibly publish datasets of various	Medium	High	S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for uploading / downloading data to medium / long storage locations through well-known protocols (FTP, WebDAV, etc.)	U1, U2, U3	Currently just temporal usage of the home-directory	Currently just temporal storage on the virtual machine	Integration with DaShaS has been completed. Data publishing is not yet
R02	Visualize raw data, resulting products and reports	High	High	S02	Each Underwater service implements task-specific reporting mechanisms	U1, U2, U3	✓	✓	✓
				S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing raw data and results	(U1), U2, U3	N	N	N
R03	To (pre- or post) process the raw data and make any required calibration / corrections	High	High	S04	Implement customizable, parametrized pipelines for pre- and post-processing the raw data	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N
				S05	Interface with external services for task-specific processing	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N
R04	Utilize high-computing power and ensure high-bandwidth access to the data	High	High	S06	Design and develop core services based on parallel computing and/or using GPGPU infrastructure	U1, U2, U3	N	N	Y
				S01	Interface with a NEANIAS data storage service for transferring data to a physically proximal location for ensuring high-bandwidth access during processing	U1, U2, U3	N	N	Y (integration with DaShaS service)
				S07	Interface with core NEANIAS services during service instantiation for requesting suitable computational resources	U1, U2, U3	N	N	Currently resources are preallocated (VM)

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Requirement				Specifications			1 st Release		
Req#	Requirement	Priority	Value	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Validated Status for U1	Validated Status for U2	Validated Status for U3
R05	Produce bathymetric maps, backscatter mosaics, photomosaics, multifrequency-based seabed classification maps and other related products	High	High	S08	Produce bathymetric maps and backscatter mosaics from multibeam echosounders.	U1	✓	-	-
				S09	Produce photomosaics and 3D models from underwater image datasets	U2	--	Y	-
				S10	Produce multifrequency-based seabed classification maps from multi-dimensional data	U3	--	-	Y
R06	Document the workflow	Medium	High	S11	Underwater services implement suitable logging mechanisms and store meta-data describing the service parametrization	U1, U2, U3	partly	Local logging available – ongoing integration with NEANIAS logging	Local logging available – ongoing integration with NEANIAS logging
				S12	Interface with AAI, auditing and other relevant NEANIAS services for collecting user-related information	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N
				S01	Interface with NEANIAS data transfer and other relevant services for storing and publishing logs and the workflow related meta-data	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N
R07	Export the results in various file formats	Low	Medium	S13	Each service offers option to serialize the produced data in widely used file formats	U1, U2, U3	N	Y	Y
				S01	Interfaces with NEANIAS data transfer services for storing the output data on suitable storage locations	U1, U2, U3	Y	N	Y
R08	To produce geospatial products/ maps with adequate with precision from interdisciplinary datasets	Medium	Medium	S09	Produce photomosaics and 3D models from underwater image datasets	U2	--	Y	-
				S02	Provide through the reporting mechanism suitable evaluation metrics for assessing the quality of the products	U1, U2, U3	partly	N	partly
R09	To have the possibility to review the geo-reference of a given dataset	Low	Medium	S14	Provide textual feedback in the UI summarizing geo-reference of the data	U1, U2, U3	partly	N	N
				S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visual feedback on the geo-reference of the data	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N

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Requirement				Specifications			1 st Release		
Req#	Requirement	Priority	Value	Spec #	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Validated Status for U1	Validated Status for U2	Validated Status for U3
R10	To achieve very high spatial accuracy in the delivered products (e.g. to the millimeter)	Medium	Medium	S09	Produce photomosaics and 3D models from underwater image datasets	U2	—	Y	—
				S02	Provide through the reporting mechanism suitable evaluation metrics for assessing the quality of the products	U1, U2, U3	partly	partly	partly
R11	To achieve high quality texture on the delivered products	Medium	Medium	S02	Provide through the reporting mechanism suitable evaluation metrics for assessing the quality of the products	U1, U2, U3	partly	N	partly
				S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visually assessing the quality of the products	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N
R12	Classify the seabed type	High	High	S10	Produce multifrequency-based seabed classification maps from multi-dimensional data capturing different seabed soil types (e.g. rock, mud, sand, clay, etc.)	U3	—	-	Y
				S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing the produced maps	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N
R13	Classify the seabed type and structure	Medium	High	S10	Produce multifrequency-based seabed classification maps along with any possible geomorphological information	U3	—	-	Y
				S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing the produced maps	U1, U2, U3	N	N	N
R14	Plan AUV/ROV trajectories	Medium	Medium	S08	Produce bathymetric maps and backscatter mosaics from multibeam echosounders.	U1	✓	-	-
				S15	Aid the navigation of underwater agents by providing spatially accurate photomosaics	U2	—	N	-

Table 3: Software requirements and current implementation at release #1

5. Summary and future steps

5.1. Summary of Evaluation Results

5.1.1. UW-BAT “Evaluation remarks by end-users

5.1.1.1. Geo-scientists Community

- ✓ The service is stable and can handle a variety of raw data formats with no issues. During this evaluation Kongsberg (.all) as well as Hypack (.HSX) and Teledyne Reson (.S7k) raw data have been tested. The service successfully converts the imported data to the default .mbXX.
- ✓ It is easy to leaf through the documentation and navigate to the original MB-SYSTEM Project.
- ✓ It is simple and quick to upload the raw data to the directory.
- ✓ This release does not provide the possibility to manually edit the data, neither inspect the sound speed profile or the attitude data and requires some additional steps in order to execute the commands. Nevertheless, there is the possibility to filter the data.
- ✓ The interface is not so user-friendly especially for people without prior experience.

5.1.1.2. Underwater Archaeology Community

The remarks on the evaluation of Service U1 (Bathymetry) concern mainly the interface, that is not yet user-friendly for a non-advanced user (i.e. an archaeologist). More precisely, the user can easily select and navigate to the front page and it was easy to review the documentation page.

However, prior to processing the code, the interface proved to be complicated and help was required from a more experienced user to start the test. Nevertheless, the instructions were clear and running again the service as a test was much easier. The uploading of data proved to be easy.

Finally, after the 4th step where we have the produced map as an optical result, the rest of the analysis is not comprehensible for an archaeologist (unable to check the results or their validity). The only comment on the produced map is that higher accuracy is required to be achieved in the next release.

In any case, when the interface is improved in the next release, we have no doubt of the value of this service for the archaeological research, as it is already obvious that the results could give insights on several archaeological issues, especially concerning landscape reconstruction and the detection of successive paleo shorelines, the study of the relative sea-level change, etc.

5.1.1.3. Renewable Energy Engineers

At this version, the U1 Service provides the capability to insert raw sonar data, grid them according to user requirements and process them for cleaning. The output includes the processed grid data, as well as a user defined map in an image file format.

Processing workflow is explained in some detail, mostly following a given example. It requires a number of commands in terminal mode which decreases usability and is prone to typing errors. User intervention is required in two different steps of the workflow, however this is a known bug that is set to be addressed in next versions.

It also seems that many of the commands could have been transparent to the user minimizing the needed effort.

The main drawbacks at this stage of the service are the lack of graphical tools for data processing and that the user has to have advanced knowledge of the MB-system software in order to be able to use it and get some useful results. Even basic changes, such as a dataset from a different sonar survey than the example, requires from the user to be aware of a number of different commands and MB-system's background workflow.

It is expected that usability and documentation will be further improved in the following versions for the service to be accessible to an audience with wider expertise.

5.1.2. UW-MOS | Evaluation remarks by all end-users

The first release of the service offers a friendly environment even for the end-users of all scientific communities with no previous experience. The documentation is detailed, explanatory and it is easy to follow each step of the process.

For the evaluation, a series of datasets (12 in total) were selected, trying to test a variety of underwater conditions (visibility, depth, sun reflections, etc) and possessing photos of different qualities and resolutions (cf. Evaluations tests and Analysis in the Appendix). In general, all the steps in the service (that are automatized) were successfully processed in a simple and direct way from the user-ends part. As a result, most datasets worked well validating the service.

End-users reported several difficulties. One of the first technical issues that was encountered, was the limitation of the number of photos to be uploaded in this release, an issue already known to be addressed in the next release. As a result, with a limited number of photos the scene that was produced as a photogrammetric result was also limited for optical observation (i.e., of archaeological or geological details), but good enough for the validation of the first release of the service. Another issue encountered by some end-users, was at the step of uploading the photos led to errors, thus each step had to be performed multiple times. Moreover, in some tests, only the high-resolution photos could pass the check image data quality process. However, the 2D mosaic worked fine in most cases (with photos of good and bad resolution – independently if

they had passed or not the check image data quality process). On the other hand, the 3D model failed in some cases (4 out of 6), as the service can only handle a very limited number of photos at the moment, as already discussed. Another difficulty was at in some instances the 2D model produced was distorted and in one instance, the 3D model task was successfully completed after a long processing time, but without texture. Finally, the process is at the moment fairly time-consuming, even when processing a limited number of photos.

Another issue reported was that in processing datasets coming from a camera of a particularly wide-angle (Gopro HERO 7 Black – Evaluation tests 8 and 9), end-users experienced a series of different technical issues. Neither the calibration of the camera worked (note, however, that the photos of the chessboard were not taken underwater), nor the checking of the image data quality. Due to these failures on the first steps, the 2D mosaic was incorrect and the 3D model didn't work. Therefore, in the next release we should try different calibration data-sets coming from underwater environments and taken with different underwater cameras to further evaluate this step.

In general, the service is simple to use with a user-friendly interface, easy to follow the steps, upload different datasets and run the tasks. Any end-user with no previous experience can already use it without difficulty. After running all above different datasets, the service is very positively evaluated. Of course, several technical issues are to be addressed in the next release, such as precision, accuracy, and steps that are not always working with specific datasets. In the next step, we would also expect the development of options of georeferencing, and of masking undesirable objects in the underwater photos, as well as editing capabilities, such as described in the user-ends requirements (cf. Table in 4.4).

For cross-referencing and evaluation, all the databases which were used for the U2_Service validation test, were also been tested in @Agisoft PhotoScan, the most commonly-used software at the moment from many scientific communities for this kind of image processing. We were thus able to compare the results in several technical issues, such as processing time, resolution and quality. The U2 service proved to possess several advantages, such as the possibility to run different tasks at the time, and not be constrained to follow specific steps, or the possibility to choose the creation of a 2D or 3D model immediately, without the need to always pass from a 2D processing of data, which was highly appreciated.

On the other hand, as this is only the first release of the service, as expected the 2D mosaics are at the moment of lower quality and resolution than the ones produced in Agisoft. Moreover, in Agisoft, the 3D models are smoother in texture and detailed and the processing time is much reduced. Finally, the different steps in Agisoft software are separated and are manually controlled, so that you can observe at which step the process

has stopped working. On the other hand, we must note that there is an effort in this EOSC service not to give any manual control of the different operations to the end-user, the advantage of this approach being mainly an effort towards simplicity of a complicated process, able to attract many non-experienced users with high-quality databases to be automatically processed.

5.1.3. UW-MAP service validation summary

5.1.3.1. UW-MAP | Evaluation remarks by Geoscientists

The main points of the feedback received by the end-users of the geoscientist's community are summarized below:

- The users expressed that the interface of the service is user-friendly and the documentation provided is easily accessible through the service itself.
- The service is efficient as the classification maps are produced in a short time.
- The generated results are straightforward so that an unexperienced user could evaluate, although the size of the maps is quite small and there is no scale bar nor colour bar.

5.1.3.2. UW-MAP | Evaluation remarks by underwater archaeologists

The end-users of the underwater archaeological community have found that the overall experience from testing the UW-MAP service is that the interface and the whole processing is very user-friendly. The service proved easy to navigate in the login page and review the documentation page, as well as to use and follow the different steps. The users found that the results are immediate and clear to check. Additionally, the classification results of the geological maps are easy to understand and optically evaluated by a non-experienced user while the classification results are consistent with the bathymetry provided. In their feedback though, they expressed that the latter observation was not possible to be cross-checked in a QGIS environment.

During the validation of version 1.0.1 of the UW-MAP service, the users of the underwater archaeological community experienced several difficulties when transferring the service results to the QGIS environment for cross-referencing and further study and analysis (see Appendix), summarized in the following:

- First, the georeferenced file presented problems in classification when transferred in QGIS (the values and the classes do not correspond).
- Moreover, by the comparison of the resulting classification maps, especially between the 4-classes maps and the 5-classes maps, we observed distinct differences in the categories of the classified material. For example, the zones of *mud sand and urchins*, *fine mud sand* and *sand with gravel* were attributed to different areas in the maps, when ran in the 4-classes process and in the 5-classes process, and sometimes we are losing the colour classification altogether (mostly in the 5-classes process – we are losing the blue colour and two other categories of

materials both become black). Thus, in the final result, the extent of the areas cannot be accurately calculated – especially valuable in monitoring studies on marine environments (with or without archaeological features).

- Furthermore, the colours attributed to different materials did not match when processed in the 4-and 5-classes process (ex. Black colour was attributed to gravel and in the map of the 5-classes process was attributed to gravel *and* sand with gravel). Therefore, when the map is transferred to a QGIS environment, the different materials cannot be distinguished any more.
- Finally, higher image resolution would be expected on the map produced in the next release.

Based on this user feedback, a new version (1.0.2) of the UW-MAP service has been deployed where the issues regarding visualization and interpretation of the classification maps in GIS environments (and especially QGIS) have been resolved.

5.1.3.3. UW-MAP end-user validation summary

Considering that the users that validated the service had no advanced knowledge on its technical aspects, based on their feedback it shows that this is undoubtedly a very efficient service to identify the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. Therefore, it is expected that this service will be appropriate and very useful for the recognition of archaeological features and geological structures, though no adapted database with distinct archaeological structures was yet used to validate the UW-MAP service, a challenge for the next release.

5.2. Future Steps

The three underwater thematic services seek for completion towards TRL 8 & EOSC integration while utilizing further core & micro services.

5.2.1. UW-BAT

The service in its current release is presently installed both, as a docker image in the Kubernetes cluster of the GARR cloud, as well as deployed in a virtual machine in the OpenStack GARR cloud. The VM version has the benefit of certain transparency to the host, which allows X11 SSH-port forwarding. The user can connect via SSH to the VM and forwards the graphical outputs to port 8888 of the users' localhost. This allows even 3D editing with tools like mbeditviz (see below).

Figure 12: Usage of 3D acceleration for X11/Motif forwarding on VM@GARR.

Disadvantage of this deployment lies in potential security issues when accessing the cloud-services host as well as in performance and scalability issues with respect of giving access to many users at the time.

On the other hand, deployments through the Kubernetes Cluster cater for enhanced concurrency and security, but currently lack support for graphics manipulation. For the 2nd release of this service we aim to further investigate these limitations and try and find possible workarounds.

Besides that, data management will be implemented by utilizing the NEANIAS NextCloud core service. Prepared workflows for several processing scenarios (e.g. MBES recorded from vessel or AUV) as Jupyter Notebooks are also listed with high priority in the timeline for the 2nd release. MB-System is capable of utilizing the Oregon State University Tide Prediction Software & models (OTPS; [10]) but the database (nc-format) request a 20 GB of permanent storage outside the services docker container (relevant work is in progress) Integration with further core services, e.g. logging and accounting, is also in the pipeline.

5.2.2. UW-MOS

The current production version provides the main 2D and 3D mapping capabilities expected for the service. In section 5.1.3 the functionality of our service is compared favourably to that of a commercial desktop solution (AgiSoft Photoscan), using a set of input data different from the one provided in the documentation's tutorials, including a large variety of underwater optical conditions. However, there is room for improvement.

Regarding service-specific topics, we are aware that the current feedback provided in the web page to end user is limited, and should be improved in the next version. For instance, the service should be able to provide visual feedback about the current processing steps, a better description of the results, and also show the input data for user validation. Some of the tests in 5.1.3 failed due to either errors in the task queue mechanism or a lack of space in the disk. We need to include some checks in our service to prevent these errors from happening. However, even if we try to solve the errors, we also noticed in 5.1.3 that the feedback provided to the user to inform about these problems is not precise enough, and the user cannot infer the cause of the failure. Also, the way of setting the different parameters of each sub-service/task must be reconsidered to be more user-friendly. We also need to link the different steps together, including, for instance, the output of the camera calibration task as an optional input in the 2D or 3D mapping steps, since this information would help during map construction. Currently, the maps generated by the service are not georeferenced, and we plan to include navigation data as an additional user parameter in order to solve this issue. Finally, the current deployment is based on Docker Swarm, but based on the higher flexibility for resource allocation provided by GARR's Kubernetes platform, we plan to move to this new orchestrator solution.

Regarding NEANIAS-specific alignment, the future steps include adhering to the NEANIAS-UI, in order to provide a unified style across services. Also, we need to include other core services in UW-MOS, such as data sharing, logging and accounting services. The case of the data sharing service is quite relevant, since currently the user data (input and results) resides on the virtual machine volume at GARR, which is limited to a specific quota that may be exceeded if many users are running the service at the same time without eliminating the space allocated by previous executions. Finally, we also want to link this service to the VD-Maps core service, in order to generate the maps resulting from the UW-MOS service in a tile-based format amenable for web visualization. This would allow us to present both 2D and 3D maps more efficiently.

5.2.3. UW-MAP

The service currently offers fully the basic functionalities for classifying seabed types from multispectral multibeam data by providing a series of pre-trained classification models. Logging and auditing functionalities are already available in a stand-alone fashion while they are expected to be further expanded and integrated with the corresponding NEANIAS logging and auditing core service (C2) in the short future, as part of an intermediate release.

In the next release (version 2) the service will be improved to accommodate more pre-processing and filtering functionalities for suitable preparing the data before performing the classification as well as offering possible post-processing tasks. Additionally, the possibility to use the C3.2 core service for serving the classification models will be considered. Moreover, the reporting of results and metadata will be further extended and offered also in machine actionable formats (e.g. JSON).

Furthermore, the usability of the service will be greatly improved, based also on the valuable feedback being collected from the users. Particularly, the visualization functionalities will be enhanced, offering to the user the possibility to zoom into the preview images by hovering or clicking on them, as well as adding optional map data layers on top of which the georeferenced results are displayed. To this end, integration with C4 (4th group of) core services for enhanced visualization will also be considered.

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AUV	Autonomous Underwater Vehicle
DL	Deep Learning
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MBES	Multibeam Echosounder
ML	Machine Learning
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RAG	Red-Amber-Green
ROV	<i>Remotely Operating Vehicle</i>
TRL	<i>Technology</i> Readiness Level
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Features Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WPS	Web Processing Service

Appendices A

Appendix A1 "Validation reports for the thematic service UW-BAT"

Appendix A2 "Validation reports for the thematic service UW-MOS"

Appendix A3 "Validation reports for the thematic service UW-MAP"

Appendix A1 “Validation reports for the thematic service UW-BAT “

NEANIAS <U1_Service > < UW_BAT > Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS <U1_Service>	Test Designed by: Teledyne	Wintersteller Paul Paul.Wintersteller@Teledyne.com
Module Name:	<UW_BAT>	Test Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<V 1.0.0>	Test Executed by: NKUA	Lampridou Danai
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution: 9 and 10 December 2020	
Test Requirements	Bathymetric Raw Data		
Service access/download	http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu/		

Test Case#	TEST-1		
Test Description¹	For this test Kongsberg raw data .all have been used. The general flow includes : a) converting the .all format to .mb59,b) plotting the raw data , c) filtering the data, d) processing the data, e)gridding and f) plotting the processed data		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 st step <Configure GMT>	Set GMT path	Ok	Case and space sensitive
2 nd step <Upload Data>	Upload to the directory 'work' the raw data	Ok	127 MB in 5 minutes
3 rd step <Plot the Raw data>	A Postscript file of the raw data	Ok	The cell was stopped in order to abort the process. When you restart the Kernel you have to run again the configuration of Generic Mapping Tools(GMT)
4 th step <Display Postscript file>	Convert the Postscript to .jpg and display it	Ok	

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5 th step <Clean the data>	Apply filter to clean the data.	Ok	All the ancillary files .esf and esf.stream have been created
6 th step <Process the data>	Creation of processed files	Ok	The processed .p.mb59 and all the ancillary files have been created
7 th step <Create a datalist >	Datalist containing the processed files	Ok	
8 th step <Create a DTM of the processed data and a postscript file>	Create a grid from the processed data and a postscript file	Ok	If you want to change the cell size you have to delete the .grd files and the datalist from the directory
9 th step <Download Sound Speed Profile >	txt file containing the ssp	Ok	

Test Case#	TEST-2		
Test Description ¹	For this test Wartsila –Elac data, acquired using Hypack 2018 have been used (.HSX). The general flow includes : a) converting the .all format to .mb59,b) plotting the raw data , c) filtering the data, d) processing the data, e)gridding and f) plotting the processed data		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes

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1 st step <Configure GMT>	Set GMT path	Ok	Case and space sensitive
2 nd step <Upload Data>	Upload to the directory 'work' the raw data	Ok	200 MB in 3 minutes
3 rd step <Plot the Raw data>	Conversion of .HSX to .mb201 Creation of the ancillary files Creation of datlist A Postscript file of the raw data	Ok	The cell was stopped in order to abort the process. When you restart the Kernel you have to run again the configuration of Generic Mapping Tools(GMT)
4 th step <Display Postscript file>	Convert the Postscript to .jpg and display it	Ok	
5 th step <Retrieve and apply SSP>	An svp file and the respective .par files when applied	Ok	
6 th step <Clean the data>	Apply filter to clean the data.	Ok	All the ancillary files .esf and esf.stream have been created
7 th step <Process the data>	Creation of processed files and the respective ancillary files	Ok	
8 th step <Create a datalist >	Datalist containing the processed files	Ok	
9 th step <Create a DTM of the processed data and a postscript file>	Create a grid from the processed data and a postscript file	Ok	The cell was stopped in order to abort the process. When you restart the Kernel you have to run again the configuration of Generic Mapping Tools(GMT)

¹Test Description should include input file format (where applicable)
 “Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.

NEANIAS <U1_Service > < UW_BAT > Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS <U1_Service>	Test Designed by: Teledyne	Wintersteller Paul Paul.Wintersteller@Teledyne.com
Module Name:	<UW_BAT>	Test Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<V 1.0.0>	Test Executed by:	Makis Ntouskos (NKUA)
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	14/12/2020
Test Requirements	Bathymetric Raw Data		
Service access/download	http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu/		

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Test Case#	TEST-1		
Test Description¹	For this test Kongsberg raw data .all have been used. The general flow includes : a) converting the .all format to .mb59,b) plotting the raw data , c) filtering the data, d) processing the data, e) gridding and f) plotting the processed data		
Preconditions			
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 st step <Configure GMT>	Set GMT path	Ok	
2 nd step <Upload Data>	Upload to the directory 'work' the raw data	Ok	Fast upload
3 rd step <Plot the Raw data>	A Postscript file of the raw data	Ok with problems	Had to restart the kernel to proceed with the following steps. The following message appears: (gio open:291): GLib-GIO-CRITICAL **: 13:15:29.272: g_dbus_connection_flush: assertion 'G_IS_DBUS_CONNECTION (connection)' failed Unable to init server: Could not connect: Connection refused # Failed to parse arguments: Cannot open display:
4 th step <Display Postscript file>	Convert the Postscript to .jpg and display it	Ok	Plot appears rotated by -90 degrees
5 th step <Clean the data>	Apply filter to clean the data.	Ok	Extremely long console output
6 th step <Process the data>	Creation of processed files	Ok	
7 th step <Create a datalist >	Datalist containing the processed files	Ok	
8 th step <Create a DTM of the processed data and a postscript file>	Create a grid from the processed data and a postscript file	Ok with problems	Had to restart the kernel as before. Plot appears rotated by -90 degrees
9 th step <Download Sound Speed Profile >	txt file containing the ssp	Ok	
General comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The amount of console output at each step seems overwhelming and it makes difficult to navigate through the notebook cells, could it be summarized in some way? 		

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resolving the problems that require the kernel restarts would help the user experience and reduce the need to provide detailed step by step guidance. Also, it would be nice to preload a sample notebook with additional comments at each step to act as a service tutorial. Finally, most of the issued commands are executed in the shell, making it difficult to define pipelines for processing the products (and side-products) in Python.
--	--

¹Test Description should include input file format (where applicable)

“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.

NEANIAS <U1_Service > < UW_BAT > Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS <U1_Service>	Test Designed by: TELEDYNE	<Author of procedures> <mail address>
Module Name:	<UW_BAT>	Test Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<V 1.0.0>	Test Executed by: AMU	<JAFAR ANBAR>
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIE S>	Date of Execution: November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020	
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account and finally multispectral multi-beam data.		
Service access/download	< http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu >		

Test Case#	TEST-1		
Test Description¹	Demo of seabed		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Login to the service	<Completed>	OK	Service UI appears and the user can easily select and navigate to the front page
Review the documentation page	<Completed>	OK	Clear to navigate and review the documentation page
1 st step: Prior to processing code	<Completed>	OK	
2 nd step: Upload Data	<Completed>	OK	

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<p>3rd step: Create a plot of the raw data, create data lists and a vessel-file</p>	<p><Completed></p>	<p>Ok</p>	<p>After this step I restarted the kernel, then in the 4th step there was an error in the display. BUT after releasing the following command: <code>%cd work</code> It was working normally for all the following steps</p>
<p>4th step: Display the postscript image on Jupyter Notebook</p>	<p><Completed></p>	<p>Ok</p>	
<p>5th step: try a first gentle and automatized cleaning for bathymetry</p>	<p><Completed></p>	<p>Ok</p>	<p>•</p>
<p>6th step: Apply the cleaning and create processed files</p>	<p><Completed></p>	<p>Ok</p>	<p>I am not sure if this step should apply some changes on the first display of the 4th step.</p>
<p>7th step: Create a processed data list</p>	<p><Completed></p>	<p>Ok</p>	<p>• The list was created successfully</p>

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8 th step: Create a grid (DTM) of the processed data & a postscript map from this grid	<Completed>	Ok	•
9 th step: Test MBLévitus	<Completed>	Ok	•
Test result	- Higher accuracy is required		

NEANIAS <U1_Service> <UW_BAT> Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS <U1_Service>	Test Designed by: TELEDYNE	<Author of procedures> <mail address>
Module Name:	<UW_BAT>	Test Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<V 1.0.0>	Test Executed by: AMU	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau>
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIE S>	Date of Execution: November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020	
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account and finally multispectral multi-beam data.		
Service access/download	< http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu >		

Test Case#	TEST-1		
Test Description¹	Demo of seabed		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Easy to follow
1 st step: Prior to processing code	<Completed>	OK	Not very user-friendly interface. Needed help from a more experience user to start the test.
2 nd step: Upload Data	<Completed>	OK	Easy process
3 rd step: Create a plot of the raw data, create data lists and a vessel-file	<Completed>	Ok	Instructions are clear, was easier to follow the steps from this point

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4 th step: Display the postscript image on Jupyter Notebook	<Completed>	Ok	
5 th step: try a first gentle and automatized cleaning for bathymetry	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After this step, not possible for an archaeologist to follow the results
6 th step: Apply the cleaning and create processed files	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
7 th step: Create a processed data list	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
8 th step: Create a grid (DTM) of the processed data & a postscript map from this grid	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
9 th step: Test MBLevitus	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
Test result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The interface of the service is not yet user-friendly for a non-advanced user (an archaeologist). It was complicated in the beginning to follow the steps (because of lack of experience), however the instructions were clear and running again the service was much easier. After the 4th step where we have the produced map as an optical result, the rest of the analysis is not comprehensible for an archaeologist (enable to check the results or their validity) - It seems that the service will be of high value for archaeological research 		

NEANIAS <U1_Service > <UW_BAT > Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS <U1_Service>	Test Designed by: TELEDYNE	<Author of procedures> <mail address>
Module Name:	<UW_BAT>	Test Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<V 1.0.0>	Test Executed by: AMU	<KALLIOPI BAIKA>

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution: November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020	
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account and finally multispectral multi-beam data.		
Service access/download	< http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu >		

Test Case#	TEST-1		
Test Description ¹	Demo of seabed		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Easy to follow and understand the basics
1 st step: Prior to processing code	<Completed>	OK	Not very user-friendly interface. Needed help from a more experienced user to start the test.
2 nd step: Upload Data	<Completed>	OK	Easy as a process
3 rd step: Create a plot of the raw data, create data lists and a vessel-file	<Completed>	Ok	Instructions are clear, was easier to follow the steps from this point <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •
4 th step: Display the postscript image on Jupyter Notebook	<Completed>	Ok	<p>The result seems very interesting! The map seems a</p>

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			bit distorted like a manta ray fish!
5 th step: try a first gentle and automatized cleaning for bathymetry	<Completed>	Ok	After this step, not possible for an archaeologist to follow the results
6 th step: Apply the cleaning and create processed files	<Completed>	Ok	No optical result to validate (but maybe, the result is on the code)
7 th step: Create a processed data list	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A data list was created successfully
8 th step: Create a grid (DTM) of the processed data & a postscript map from this grid	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No grid appeared or a postscript map (but maybe we should not expect an optical result?)
9 th step: Test MBLevitus	<Completed>	Ok	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unable to understand this step or evaluate a result (as an archaeologist)
Test result	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The interface of the service is not yet user-friendly for a non-advanced user (an archaeologist). It was complicated in the beginning to follow the steps (because of lack of experience), however the instructions were clear and running again the service as a test was much easier. - After the 4th step where we have the produced map as an optical result, the rest of the analysis is not comprehensible for an archaeologist (enable to check the results or their validity) - It seems that the service will be of high value for archaeological research 		

U1_Service Evaluation remarks by end-users (underwater archaeological community)

The remarks on the evaluation of Service U1 (Bathymetry) concern mainly the interface, that is not yet user-friendly for a non-advanced user (i.e. an archaeologist). More precisely, the user can easily select and navigate to the front page and it was easy to review the documentation page. However, prior to processing the code, the interface proved to be complicated and help was required from a more experienced user to start the test. Nevertheless, the instructions were clear and running again the service as a test was much easier. The uploading of data proved to be easy. Finally, after the 4th step where we have the produced map as an optical result, the rest of the analysis is not comprehensible for an archaeologist (enable to check the results or their validity). The

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only comment on the produced map is that higher accuracy is required to be achieved in the next release.

In any case, when the interface is improved in the next release, we have no doubt of the value of this service for the archaeological research, as it is already obvious that the results could give insights on several archaeological issues, especially concerning landscape reconstruction and the detection of successive paleoshorelines, the study of the relative sea-level change, etc.

NEANIAS <U1_Service > < UW_BAT > Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS <U1_Service>	Test Designed by: Teledyne	Wintersteller Paul Paul.Wintersteller@Teledyne.com
Module Name:	<UW_BAT>	Test Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<V 1.0.0>	Test Executed by:	Angelos Mallios (Eunice)
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution:	16/12/2020
Test Requirements	Bathymetric Raw Data		
Service access/download	http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu/		

Test Case#	TEST-1		
Test Description¹	For this test Kongsberg raw data .all have been used. The general flow includes: a) converting the .all format to .mb59,b) plotting the raw data , c) filtering the data, d) processing the data, e) gridding and f) plotting the processed data		
Preconditions			
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 st step <Configure GMT>	Set GMT path	Ok	
2 nd step <Upload Data>	Upload to the directory 'work' the raw data	Ok	Fast upload. No instructions or intuitive options for uploading and creating datalist with data from other type of sonar. The defaults from the example instructions was used.
3 rd step <Plot the Raw data>	A Postscript file of the raw data	Ok with problems	Had to restart the kernel to proceed with the following steps and run again the configuration of GMT (mentioned in the instructions).
4 th step <Display Postscript file>	Convert the Postscript to .jpg and display it	Ok	Plot appears rotated by -90 degrees

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5 th step <Clean the data>	Apply filter to clean the data.	Ok	No instructions or intuitive options for cleaning the data. The defaults from the example instructions was used.
6 th step <Process the data>	Creation of processed files	Ok	
7 th step <Create a datalist >	Datalist containing the processed files	Ok	
8 th step <Create a DTM of the processed data and a postscript file>	Create a grid from the processed data and a postscript file	Ok with problems	Had to restart the kernel to proceed with the following steps and run again the configuration of GMT (mentioned in the instructions). Plot appears rotated by -90 degrees

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			<p>Almost all data have been filtered with the default settings of the example.</p>
<p>9th step <Download Sound Speed Profile ></p>	<p>txt file containing the ssp</p>	<p>Ok</p>	
<p>General comments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At this state, the service can be used only from expert users of MB-system. • Very important MB-system graphical tools for data processing are not supported. 		

¹Test Description should include input file format (where applicable)
“Actual outcome”, **“notes”** and **“test result”** are compiled by the validator.

Appendix A2 “Validation reports for the thematic service UW-MOS “

NEANIAS <U1_Service > < UW_BAT > Validation TEST LOG

Project Name:	NEANIAS <U1_Service>	Test Designed by: Teledyne	Wintersteller Paul Paul.Wintersteller@Teledyne.com
Module Name:	<UW_BAT>	Test Designed date:	<Date>
Release Version:	<V 1.0.0>	Test Executed by: NKUA	Lampridou Danai
Dependencies:	<LIST-DEPENDENCIES>	Date of Execution: 9 and 10 December 2020	
Test Requirements	Bathymetric Raw Data		
Service access/download	http://bathyprocessing.dev.neanias.eu/		

Test Case#	TEST-1		
Test Description¹	For this test Kongsberg raw data .all have been used. The general flow includes : a) converting the .all format to .mb59,b) plotting the raw data , c) filtering the data, d) processing the data, e)gridding and f) plotting the processed data		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 st step <Configure GMT>	Set GMT path	Ok	Case and space sensitive
2 nd step <Upload Data>	Upload to the directory 'work' the raw data	Ok	127 MB in 5 minutes
3 rd step <Plot the Raw data>	A Postscript file of the raw data	Ok	The cell was stopped in order to abort the process. When you restart the Kernel you have to run again the configuration of Generic Mapping Tools(GMT)
4 th step <Display Postscript file>	Convert the Postscript to .jpg and display it	Ok	
5 th step <Clean the data>	Apply filter to clean the data.	Ok	All the ancillary files .esf and esf.stream have been created
6 th step <Process the data>	Creation of processed files	Ok	The processed .p.mb59 and all the ancillary files have been created
7 th step <Create a datalist >	Datalist containing the processed files	Ok	
8 th step <Create a DTM of the processed data and a postscript file>	Create a grid from the processed data and a postscript file	Ok	If you want to change the cell size you have to delete the .grd files and the datalist from the directory

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9 th step <Download Sound Speed Profile >	txt file containing the ssp	Ok	
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Test Case#	TEST-2		
Test Description¹	For this test Wartsila –Elac data, acquired using Hypack 2018 have been used (.HSX). The general flow includes : a) converting the .all format to .mb59,b) plotting the raw data , c) filtering the data, d) processing the data, e)gridding and f) plotting the processed data		
Preconditions	<Precondition for test, e.g., previous test complete>		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1 st step <Configure GMT>	Set GMT path	Ok	Case and space sensitive
2 nd step <Upload Data>	Upload to the directory 'work' the raw data	Ok	200 MB in 3 minutes
3 rd step <Plot the Raw data>	Conversion of .HSX to .mb201 Creation of the ancillary files Creation of datlist A Postscript file of the raw data	Ok	The cell was stopped in order to abort the process. When you restart the Kernel you have to run again the configuration of Generic Mapping Tools(GMT)
4 th step <Display Postscript file>	Convert the Postscript to .jpg and display it	Ok	
5 th step <Retrieve and apply SSP>	An svp file and the respective .par files when applied	Ok	
6 th step <Clean the data>	Apply filter to clean the data.	Ok	All the ancillary files .esf and esf.stream have been created
7 th step <Process the data>	Creation of processed files and the respective ancillary files	Ok	
8 th step <Create a datalist >	Datalist containing the processed files	Ok	
9 th step <Create a DTM of the processed data and a postscript file>	Create a grid from the processed data and a postscript file	Ok	The cell was stopped in order to abort the process. When you restart the Kernel you have to run again the configuration of Generic Mapping Tools(GMT)

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¹Test Description should include input file format (where applicable)
 “Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com josepqp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Josep Quintana (CORONIS)
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	11/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
4. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
5. Set Parameters:	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	It would be good to disable charuco calibration buttons

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			when using chessboard pattern
6. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
7. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	OK	
8. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	OK	
9. Click on “ Download Reprojection Data ” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points reprojected on the image and both combined	OK	
10. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	OK	
11. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
4. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
6. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	
7. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	

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4. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
6. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
7. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
8. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	
9. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	

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4. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
6. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	OK	
7. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	OK	It would be good to be able to see the result on the web browser
8. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

* “Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com josepgp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Makis Ntouskos (NKUA)
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	2/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
12. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	Login expires very fast
13. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Could not find link on the UI pointing to the documentation
14. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
15. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	Demo dataset contains a 11x11 chessboard pattern
16. Set Parameters: 	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	Used values mentioned in the documentation (11x11 0.056m)
17. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
18. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	OK	
19. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	OK	
20. Click on “ Download Reprojection Data ” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

	reprojected on the image and both combined		
21. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	OK	
22. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Worked as expected		

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
8. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	Login expires very fast
9. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Could not find link on the UI pointing to the documentation
10. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
11. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
12. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
13. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	

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14. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Worked as expected		

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
10. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	Login expires very fast
11. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Could not find link on the UI pointing to the documentation
12. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
13. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
14. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	A progress bar would be useful as the task execution takes considerable time
15. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
16. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
17. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	

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18. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Worked as expected		

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
9. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	Login expires very fast
10. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Could not find link on the UI pointing to the documentation
11. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
12. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
13. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	A progress bar would be useful as the task execution takes considerable time
14. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	OK	
15. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	OK	
16. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Worked as expected		

U2_Service Evaluation remarks by end-users (underwater archaeological community)

Photomosaicing for underwater photogrammetry is a common documentation method for underwater archaeology, as it can produce time-saving, 3D accuracy results maximising the dive-time documentation data (cf. Historiography, goals and objectives in D.2.1). Therefore, most maritime archaeologists use different softwares and are familiar with the photogrammetric process. The most commonly used software are @Agisoft PhotoScan and Agisoft Metashape.

Therefore, for immediate cross-referencing and evaluation, all the databases which were used for the U2_Service validation test, were also been tested in Agisoft PhotoScan before being uploaded to the service. We were thus able to compare the results between the two services in several issues, such as processing time, resolution and quality.

The selection and quality of the datasets

The first release of the service provides different processing and reconstruction steps for underwater scenes based on optical/image data:

- Calibration of the camera
- Check image data quality
- Create a 2D image mosaic
- Create a 3D model

Thus, a series of datasets (9 in total) were selected for the validation test, trying to evaluate a variety of underwater conditions and different qualities of photos (cf. all test evaluations in the Appendix). Almost all datasets were taken from photogrammetric databases from Aigina Harbour-city Project 2019-2023, a submerged ancient harbour-city in the Aegean Sea lying today in shallow waters (max. depth of the documented structured max. -3.00 m). Test 7 was taken from a submerged harbour-city on the coast of Attica studied in the framework of Submerged Attica Project (Aegean Sea, Greece). In both sites, the visibility is good.

Firstly, the underwater photos of each dataset were acquired with three different cameras (Gopro HERO 7 Black, Nikon D700 and Sony DSC-RX100) in JPEG format. The sea conditions were also different presenting various challenges: Presence or not of strong or medium sun reflections, occasional shadows, good or bad visibility and various depths (always in shallow waters).

On the selection of the databases, one of the first technical issues we encountered was the limitation of the number of the photos to be uploaded. Only a number of maximum of 30 photos in high resolution could be uploaded, thus we had occasionally to resize the original photos. On the other hand, with a limited number of photos the archaeological scene that was produced as a photogrammetric result was also limited for optical observation (of archaeological details), but good enough for the validation of the first release of the service.

Evaluation of different datasets according to different cameras

Evaluation Tests 1 to 6 (Nikon D700)

Six validation tests were processed with photos taken with this camera, the scenes include submerged structures with architectural details at a max-depth of - 2 m. We provided no calibration photos for these tests, as in Agisoft software that were initially processed, this calibration was not needed. All photos were corrected in Adobe Photoshop-Light room.

Test 1 and 2 concern the documentation of the same structure, the difference being the presence of sun reflection in Test 1 and controlled shadow in Test 2. In general, in Tests 1 and 2, datasets with photos of good resolution, taken in very good visibility worked well validating the service.

The encountered difficulties are the following: Only the high-resolution photos could pass the check image data quality process. However, the 2D mosaic worked fine in both cases (with photos of good and bad resolution). The 3D model failed in both cases. Finally, in the Test 1, after repetition, the 3D model worked only when the photos were reduced to 14 in number (instead of 27) - the whole process took 30 minutes.

Thus, as a result, all the steps in the service were successfully processed.

Tests 3 and 4 concern the same dataset of photos from an archaeological structure (harbour fortification section). In the first instance 20 photos of high resolution taken in a good visibility, the steps failed (neither the Check image data quality nor the 2D mosaic or 3D model).

Therefore, the test was repeated (called Test 4) with the same photos but in a lower resolution. The only difference is that the Check image data quality worked, the values were more than 500 and the photos were valid.

As a result, we observed that in comparison with the Tests 1 and 2, this time we had the opposite result. The low-resolution photos of Test 2 didn't pass the quality check, but in the Test 4 the low-resolution photos passed. On the opposite, the high-resolution photos of Test 1 were successfully processed, but in Test 3, the high-resolution photos had to be downgraded in order to be processed successfully.

In Test 5, 12 photos of medium resolution and of good visibility belonging to the foundation of an archaeological structure (Aigina Military Harbour- SR5) were processed with variable results. We observed that though the check image data quality didn't work and the photos were considered not valid (the values were not more than 500- all the values were red), the 2D mosaic was completed successfully. Finally, the 3D model step didn't work.

In Test-6, a number of 10 photos of high resolution taken in good visibility and belonging to the foundation of an archaeological structure (Aigina Military Harbour- SR6) gave different results. The first steps worked well. Check image data quality validated all photos and the 2D mosaic was completed, however the model was distorted (because the photos were not vertical?). Nevertheless, the 3D model task was completed with a good result, but for the first time without texture (processing time 2h:40)

As a general observation, out of the 6 tests with photos taken with this camera, the 3D model didn't work in 4 cases out of 6

Comparison with @Agisoft Photoscan software

All 6 datasets run successfully in @Agisoft with good results in the 2D and 3D models.

The comparison of the first release of the U2 service with the Agisoft results are the following:

- The 2D mosaics are of lower quality and resolution than the ones produced in Agisoft.
- The 3D model of Test 1 is less smooth and detailed than in Agisoft.
- The processing time in Agisoft is much reduced for the final result.

Evaluation Test 7 (Sony DSC-RX100)

One validation test was taken with this camera, the scene includes a ceramic pipeline with archaeological details lying at a max. depth of -1 m from a submerged harbour-city on the coast of Attica (Aegean Sea, Greece).

The test involved 19 photos, of medium resolution taken in a good visibility, however, there was some sun reflections. No calibration photos were provided. In the process, the check image data quality step didn't work (there were no values in the results table). However, the 2D mosaic was completed but it was distorted (because the photos were not vertical?). The 3D model task did not work.

Evaluation Tests 8 and 9 (Gopro HERO 7 Black)

Two validation tests were processed with photos taken with this camera (see Appendix), both scenes include submerged archaeological structures (foundation walls constructed with blocs bearing architectural details) at a max-depth of -1.5 m.

In the first test, 28 photos were selected from a documentation with good visibility underwater. The resolution of the photos were downgraded to medium, so that they could be uploaded to the service. In the second test, 20 photos of high resolution were processed. In both cases, the photos are the originals, no light-editing was applied.

In processing these two datasets coming from a camera of a particularly wide-angle, we experienced a series of technical issues. Neither the calibration of the camera worked (note that the photos of the chessboard were not taken underwater), nor the checking of the image date quality. Due to these failures on the first steps, the 2D mosaic was incorrect and the 3D model didn't work at all after 2 hours, while it did go through the following processes:

- Computing features
- Computing all-against-all matches
- Incremental SFM
- Refine sparse 3D
- Densify 3D cloud
- Surface reconstruction
- Texture mapping

For comparison, the photos of the same two datasets were processed in Agisoft software, even without calibration of the camera: All the results were valid and the 2D and 3D models were produced correctly. Moreover, we should observe that the different steps in the processing already described, in Agisoft software, are separated and are manually controlled, so that you can observe at which step the process has stopped working.

General results

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The service is simple to use with a user-friendly interface, easy to follow the steps, upload different datasets and run the tasks. An underwater archaeologist can already use it without any difficulty. It is a fact, that after running all above different data-sets (see details in the Appendix) the service is very positively evaluated and is working with success. Of course, several technical issues are to be considered in the next release, such as precision, accuracy, and steps that are not always working with specific datasets. In the next step we would also expect georeferencing, options of masking undesirable objects in the underwater photos and editing capabilities, as described in the user-ends requirements (cf. Table in 4.1).

Finally, we must note that there is an effort not to give any manual control of the different operations to the users– which is a difference from the softwares that we are used to work with- however there are also advantages in this approach, mainly an effort towards simplicity.

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppq@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Nuno Gracias (CORONIS)
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	13/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

23. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
24. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
25. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
26. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
27. Set Parameters: 	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	
28. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
29. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	OK	
30. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	OK	
31. Click on “ Download Reprojection Data ” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points reprojected on the image and both combined	OK	
32. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

33. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Would be nice to see the input data in addition to the results. Also, when uploading the data, the user should be notified about the uploading progress.		

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
15. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
16. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
17. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
18. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
19. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
20. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	
21. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Would be nice to see the input data in addition to the results. Also, when uploading the data, the user should be notified about the uploading progress.		

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
19. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
20. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
21. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
22. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
23. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
24. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
25. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
26. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	
27. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Would be nice to see the input data in addition to the results		

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)
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 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
17. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
18. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
19. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
20. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
21. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
22. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	OK	
23. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	OK	
24. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Would be nice to see the input data in addition to the results. Also, when uploading the data, the user should be notified about the uploading progress.		

* **“Actual outcome”**, **“notes”** and **“test result”** are compiled by the validator.

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com josepgp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Rafael Garcia (CORONIS)
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	12/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
34. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
35. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
36. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
37. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
38. Set Parameters:	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

39. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
40. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	OK	
41. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	OK	
42. Click on “Download Reprojection Data” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points reprojected on the image and both combined	OK	
43. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	OK	
44. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
22. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
23. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
24. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

25. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
26. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	The user should be updated on the execution progress somehow
27. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	
28. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
28. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
29. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
30. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
31. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
32. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	The user should be updated on the execution progress somehow

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

33. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
34. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
35. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	
36. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
25. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
26. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
27. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
28. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
29. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	While in this case the current step is shown to the user a measure of the expected remaining execution time would be appreciated

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

30. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	OK	
31. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	OK	
32. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

* “*Actual outcome*”, “*notes*” and “*test result*” are compiled by the validator.

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppq@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS)
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	11/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

45. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
46. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
47. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
48. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
<p>49. Set Parameters:</p>	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	
50. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
51. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	OK	
52. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	OK	
53. Click on “ Download Reprojection Data ” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points reprojected on the image and both combined	OK	
54. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	OK	

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55. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
29. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
30. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
31. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
32. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
33. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
34. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	
35. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003
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 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

(2D Image Mosaic)			
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
37. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
38. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
39. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
40. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
41. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
42. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
43. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
44. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	
45. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
33. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
34. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
35. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
36. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
37. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
38. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	OK	
39. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	OK	
40. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com josepgp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-1

Photogrammetry of archaeological structure-Shipshed SR9 AIGINA HARBOUR CITY PROJECT 2020

The photogrammetry consists of 27 photos in JPEG format taken with NIKON D700 camera. The resolution of the photos is high. The visibility is very good. The photos were edited with Adobe Photoshop-Light room.

The scene includes structures of blocks with architectural details and the max-depth is 1.0 m. The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
56. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
57. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
58. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

59. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service		There are no photos of the chessboard taken by this camera underwater
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Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
36. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
37. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
38. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
39. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
40. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
41. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	The values were more than 500 and the photos were valid.
42. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

46. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
47. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
48. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
49. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
50. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
51. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
52. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
53. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	
54. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	The 2D mosaic is less in quality and resolution than in Agisoft.		

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
41. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
42. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
43. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
44. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
45. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
46. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	27 Photos, After 2h:30 <ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -9>
47. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	27 Photos, After 2h:30 <ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -9>
48. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	OK	14 Photos, After 30min

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

49. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	The 3D model is less smooth and detailed than in Agisoft. The time in Agisoft is much less.		

* “Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppq@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-2

Photogrammetry of archaeological structure-Shipshed SR9 AIGINA HARBOUR CITY PROJECT 2020

The photogrammetry consists of 28 photos in JPEG format taken with NIKON D700 camera. The resolution of the photos is medium due to the need of upload the photos to the service. The visibility is very good but there is some sun reflection. The photos were edited with Adobe Photoshop-Light room.

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

The scene includes structures of blocks with architectural details and the max-depth is 1.0 m.
 The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
60. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
61. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
62. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
63. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service		There are no photos of the chessboard taken by this camera underwater

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
43. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
44. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
45. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
46. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

47. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
48. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	Fail	ERROR in Celery:'ascii' codec can't encode characters in position 23-24: ordinal not in range(128)>
49. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
55. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
56. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
57. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
58. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
59. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
60. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
61. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

62. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	The photos are not vertical, Test only the 3D model, therefore the 2D mosaic is distorted.
63. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	The 2D mosaic worked even though the check image data quality didn't work.		

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
50. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
51. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
52. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
53. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

54. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
55. Click on "Download" button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	ERROR in Celery:Worker exited prematurely: signal 11 (SIGSEGV)>
56. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	ERROR in Celery:Worker exited prematurely: signal 11 (SIGSEGV)>
57. Click on "Delete" button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	<p>The 3D model didn't work. Through the processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computing features - Computing all-against-all matches - Incremental SFM - Refine sparse 3D - Densify 3D cloud - Surface reconstruction - Texture mapping <p>In this case it is better to have more flexibility instead of waiting for 2 hours without any results. In Agisoft, these steps are separated so you can figure out if the 3D model will work or not.</p>		

* *"Actual outcome", "notes" and "test result" are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppq@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-3

**Photogrammetry submerged fortification 1st test
AIGINA HARBOUR CITY PROJECT 2020**

The photogrammetry consists of 20 photos in JPEG format taken with NIKON D700 camera. The resolution of the photos is high. The visibility is very good. The photos were edited with Adobe Photoshop-Light room.

The scene includes structures of blocks with architectural details and the max-depth is 1.5 m.

The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
64. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
65. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

66. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
67. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service		There are no photos of the chessboard taken by this camera underwater

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
50. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
51. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
52. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
53. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
54. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
55. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	Fail	There were no values in the results table
56. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
64. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
65. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
66. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
67. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
68. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
69. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
70. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
71. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	Fail	The photos are not vertical, Test only the 3D model.
72. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

58. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
59. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
60. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
61. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
62. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
63. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -9
64. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -9
65. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	<p>The 3D model didn't work after about 1h:30m. Through the processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computing features - Computing all-against-all matches - Incremental SFM - Refine spare 3D - Densify 3D cloud - Surface reconstruction - Texture mapping <p>In this case it is better to have more flexibility instead of waiting for 2 hours without any results. In Agisoft, these steps are separated so you can figure out if the 3D model will work or not.</p>		

* **“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result”** are compiled by the validator.

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com josepqp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-4

**Photogrammetry submerged fortification 2nd test
AIGINA HARBOUR CITY PROJECT 2020**

The photogrammetry consists of 20 photos in JPEG format taken with NIKON D700 camera. The resolution of the photos is medium due to the need of upload the photos to the service. The visibility is very good. The photos were edited with Adobe Photoshop-Light room. The scene includes structures of blocks with architectural details and the max-depth is 1.5 m. The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

68. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
69. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
70. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
71. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service		There are no photos of the chessboard taken by this camera underwater

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
57. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
58. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
59. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
60. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
61. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
62. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	The values were more than 500 and the photos were valid.

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

63. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
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Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
73. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
74. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
75. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
76. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
77. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
78. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
79. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
80. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -6
81. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
66. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
67. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
68. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
69. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
70. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
71. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -6
72. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -6
73. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	This test was repeated with the same photos but in a low resolution this time, due to the need of upload the photos to the service. The only difference is		

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	<p>that the Check image data quality worked, the values were more than 500 and the photos were valid. The 3D model didn't work after 1h:40m. Through the processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computing features - Computing all-against-all matches - Incremental SFM - Refine sparse 3D - Densify 3D cloud - Surface reconstruction - Texture mapping <p>In this case it is better to have more flexibility instead of waiting for 2 hours without any results. In Agisoft, these steps are separated so you can figure out if the 3D model will work or not.</p>
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* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppq@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-5

Photogrammetry of archaeological structure-Shipshed SR5 AIGINA HARBOUR CITY PROJECT 2019

The photogrammetry consists of 12 photos in JPEG format taken with NIKON D700 camera. The resolution of the photos is medium due to the need of upload the photos to the service. The visibility is very good. The photos were edited with Adobe Photoshop-Light room. The scene includes structures of blocks with architectural details and the max-depth is 1.5 m. The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
72. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
73. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
74. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
75. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service		There are no photos of the chessboard taken by this camera underwater

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
64. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
65. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	

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66. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
67. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
68. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
69. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	Fail	The values were not more than 500 and the photos were not validated. ALL Red
70. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
82. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
83. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
84. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
85. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	

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86. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
87. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
88. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
89. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	
90. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	In this test, though the photos were invalid and the quality check was invalid (ALL Red), the 2D mosaic was completed with good results.		

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
74. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	

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75. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
76. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
77. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
78. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
79. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : 1
80. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : 1
81. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com josepgp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-6

Photogrammetry of archaeological structure-Shipshed SR6 AIGINA HARBOUR CITY PROJECT 2019

The photogrammetry consists of 10 photos in JPEG format taken with NIKON D700 camera. The resolution of the photos is high. The visibility is very good but there is some sun reflection. The photos were edited with Adobe Photoshop-Light room. The scene includes structures of blocks with architectural details and the max-depth is 1.0 m. The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
76. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
77. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
78. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

79. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service		There are no photos of the chessboard taken by this camera underwater
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Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
71. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
72. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
73. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
74. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
75. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
76. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	The values were more than 500 and the photos were valid.
77. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes

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91. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
92. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
93. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
94. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
95. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
96. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
97. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
98. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	<p>The photos are not vertical so the 2D mosaic is distorted</p>
99. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data	OK	

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	from the already executed task		
Test result			

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
82. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
83. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
84. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
85. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
86. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
87. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	OK	
88. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	

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			The 3D model was without texture
89. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	<p>The 3D model task was completed and the result is OK. The model is without texture. After 2h:40m</p> <p>Same input in Agisoft after only 20min.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> </div>		

* “Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppq@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-7

**Photogrammetry of archaeological remains (Pipe)
SUBMERGED ATTICA PROJECT 2019**

The photogrammetry consists of 19 photos in JPEG format taken with Sony DSC-RX100 camera. The resolution of the photos is medium due to the need of upload the photos to the service. The visibility is good but there is some sun reflection. The scene includes ceramics and the max-depth is 1.0 m. The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
80. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
81. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
82. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
83. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service		There are no photos of the chessboard taken by this camera underwater

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
78. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
79. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	

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80. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
81. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
82. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
83. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	Fail	There were no values in the results table
84. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
100. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
101. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
102. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
103. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	

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104. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
105. Click on "See the result" button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
106. Click on "Download" button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
107. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	<p>The photos are not vertical so the 2D mosaic is distorted.</p>
108. Click on "Delete" button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
90. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
91. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

92. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
93. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
94. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
95. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	ERROR in Celery: list index out of range
96. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	ERROR in Celery: list index out of range
97. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	<p>The 3D model didn't work. Through the processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computing features - Computing all-against-all matches - Incremental SFM - Refine sparse 3D - Densify 3D cloud - Surface reconstruction - Texture mapping <p>In this case it is better to have more flexibility instead of waiting for 2 hours without any results. In Agisoft, these steps are separated so you can figure out if the 3D model will work or not.</p>		

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-8

**Photogrammetry of archaeological objects in situ
SUBMERGED ATTICA PROJECT 2019**

The photogrammetry consists of 28 photos in JPEG format taken with GoPro HERO 7 Black camera. The resolution of the photos is medium due to the need of upload the photos to the service. The visibility is good. The photos are the original photos, there is no light editing.

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The scene includes different archaeological objects (Ceramics and stone structures) and the max-depth is 1.5 m.

The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
84. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
85. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
86. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
87. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
88. Set Parameters: 	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	
89. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
90. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	Fail	The photos of the chessboard were not taken under water
91. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	Fail	

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92. Click on “ Download Reprojection Data ” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points reprojected on the image and both combined	Fail	
93. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	Fail	
94. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Note the photos for the calibration were also tested in Agisoft.		

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
85. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
86. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
87. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
88. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
89. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	

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90. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	Fail	There were no values in the results table
91. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	...

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
109. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
110. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
111. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
112. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
113. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
114. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
115. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	

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116. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	<p>The photos are not vertical so the 2D mosaic is distorted</p>
117. Click on "Delete" button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	The 2D mosaic is not correct based on the failure of the previous two tasks.		

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
98. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
99. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
100. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
101. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

102. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
103. Click on "Download" button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	ERROR in Celery: list index out of range
104. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	ERROR in Celery: list index out of range
105. Click on "Delete" button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	<p>The 3D model didn't work. Through the processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computing features - Computing all-against-all matches - Incremental SFM - Refine sparse 3D - Densify 3D cloud - Surface reconstruction - Texture mapping <p>In this case it is better to have more flexibility instead of waiting for 2 hours without any results. In Agisoft, these steps are separated so you can figure out if the 3D model will work or not.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> </div> <p>Agisoft 3D model (Same input) and without calibration</p>		

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Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MOS (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com josepgp@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MOS	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	<Jean-Christophe Sourisseau> <Kalliopi Baika> <Jafar Anbar> <Labrini Tsitsou> AMU
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	November 19, 2020 until December 10, 2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account. Optical/Image data		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test-9

Photogrammetry submerged structure K2 SUBMERGED ATTICA PROJECT 2019

The photogrammetry consists of 20 photos in JPEG format taken with GoPro HERO 7 Black camera. The resolution of the photos is good. The visibility is good. The photos are the original photos, there is no light editing.

The scene includes submerged structures and the max-depth is 1.5 m.

The photogrammetry was tested on Agisoft Photo scan software with no problems.

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
95. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
96. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
97. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

98. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
99. Set Parameters: 	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	
100. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
101. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	Fail	The photos of the chessboard were not taken under water
102. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	Fail	
103. Click on “ Download Reprojection Data ” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points reprojected on the image and both combined	Fail	
104. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	Fail	
105. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	Note the photos for the calibration were also tested in Agisoft.		

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)
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 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
92. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
93. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
94. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
95. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
96. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
97. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	Fail	There were no values in the results table
98. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	...

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
118. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
119. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

120. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
121. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
122. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
123. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
124. Click on “ Download ” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
125. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	Fail	ERROR: Execution failed with return code = : -9
126. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	<p>Agisoft 2D mosaic (Same input)</p>		

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)
Preconditions	None

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
106. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
107. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
108. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
109. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
110. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
111. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	Fail	ERROR in Celery: list index out of range
112. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	Fail	RROR in Celery: list index out of range
113. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result	<p>The 3D model didn't work.</p> <p>Through the processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computing features - Computing all-against-all matches - Incremental SFM - Refine spare 3D - Densify 3D cloud - Surface reconstruction - Texture mapping <p>In this case it is better to have more flexibility instead of waiting for 2 hours without any results.</p> <p>In Agisoft, these steps are separated so you can figure out if the 3D model will work or not.</p>		

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

* “Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U2) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-mos.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Ricard Campos (CORONIS) Josep Quintana (CORONIS) Rafael Garcia (CORONIS) ricardcd@gmail.com joseppq@gmail.com rafael.garcia100@gmail.com
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Effie Zafeirakopoulou (NKUA)
Dependencies:	✓ NEANIAS AAI	Date of Execution:	12/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-mos.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u2-service		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MOS-001 (Calibration)		
Test Description	Camera Calibration with 10 x 10 chessboard pattern using Demo Data (from Documentation)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
106. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
107. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

108. Select Calibrate Camera	User can select calibration camera option	OK	
109. Select a set of calibration images	User can download 10 x 10 chessboard pattern (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
110. Set Parameters: 	User can select the calibration parameters	OK	
111. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
112. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. Calibration data will appear on the browser	OK	
113. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A json file containing calibration data will be downloaded	OK	
114. Click on “Download Reprojection Data” button	User can select to download result and reprojection file. A zip file containing: pattern detected on images, points reprojected on the image and both combined	OK	
115. Compare calibration result with calibration data provided on the documentation	Calibration data is consistent with already provided results	OK	
116. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MOS-002 (Image Data Quality)		
Test Description	Check image quality using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
99. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
100. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
101. Select Check Image Data Quality	User can select to check the quality of the data	OK	
102. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
103. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
104. Click on “ See the result ” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A list of images and number of detected features should be provided (the ones with lower values are highlighted)	OK	
105. Click on “ Delete ” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MOS-003 (2D Image Mosaic)		
Test Description	Create 2D image mosaic using Demo Data (from mosaic data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

127. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
128. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
129. Select Create a 2D Mosaic	User can select to create a 2D mosaic	OK	
130. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_2d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
131. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
132. Click on “See the result” button and inspect result	User can select to see result. A 2D mosaic will appear on the browser	OK	
133. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A png file will be downloaded	OK	
134. Compare 2D mosaic result with documentation result	2D mosaic result is consistent with already provided results	OK	
135. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #4	TEST-UW-MOS-004 (3D Model)		
Test Description	Create 3D model using Demo Data (from 3D Model data)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
114. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

115. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
116. Select Create a 3D Model	User can select to create a 3D model	OK	
117. Select a set of underwater images	User can download uw-mos_3d_demo_data (link) and upload them to the service	OK	
118. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. A new window will appear with all tasks	OK	
119. Click on “Download” button	User can select to download result. A ply file will be downloaded	OK	
120. Compare 3D model result with documentation result	3D model can be seen using meshlab software, the result should be the same than the one provided on the documentation	OK	
121. Click on “Delete” button	User can select to delete all existing data from the already executed task	OK	
Test result			

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own optical datasets

Appendix A3 - “Validation reports for the thematic service UW-MAP”

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U3) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-map.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Panagiotis Mertikas (NKUA) Valsamis Ntouskos (NKUA) Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA) panag.mertikas@gmail.com ntouskos@mail.ntua.gr karank@central.ntua.gr
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	JAFAR ANBAR AMU
Dependencies:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ NEANIAS AAI ✓ NEANIAS DaShaS (Nextcloud) 	Date of Execution:	09/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-map.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MAP-001 (Demo Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Three classes using Demo Data (from Patricia Bay)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
117. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	Nice and easy
118. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Efficient and easy to follow
119. Select Demo Dataset (patricia_demo.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Patricia for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI list	OK	
120. Select “ Three Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 3 for this experiment)	OK	

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

<p>121. Execute the service</p>	<p>User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Sand, Mud Sand, Gravel) 	<p>OK</p>	<p>Very efficient</p>
<p>122. Compare classification result with provided geological map</p>	<p>Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map</p>	<p>OK</p>	<p>The classification results are simple and clear</p>
<p>123. Click on “Download result” button and inspect downloaded classification map</p>	<p>The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 3 classes (labels)</p>	<p>OK</p>	<p>Higher accuracy is required.</p> <p>The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 3. The values start from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0) (The black background of the tiff file) - (1-2-3) values correspond to the classified classes. - (From 4 to 255) represent nothing?? <p>Check FIG.1</p>
<p>Test result</p>	<p>User-friendly service. Efficient to understand the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. Probably it will be easy to recognize the presence of the archaeological remains in the context of classification. There are some technical problems to be solved according to the downloaded files.</p>		

<p>Test Case #2</p>	<p>TEST-UW-MAP-002 (Validation Data)</p>
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Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Description	Classification with Four classes using Validation Data (from Patricia Bay)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Demo Dataset (newbex.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Newbex for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
4. Select " Four Classes " model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 4 for this experiment)	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	Very efficient
6. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	The classification results are simply clear
7. Click on " Download result " button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 4 classes (labels)	OK	Higher accuracy is required and the gravel class is in black. The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 4. The values start from

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0) (The black background of the tiff file). - (1-2-3) values correspond to the classified classes. - (4) value is in black and corresponds to the gravel class. - (From 5 to 255) are black also, but they represent nothing?? <p style="background-color: yellow; display: inline-block;">Check FIG.2</p>
Test result	<p>User-friendly service. Efficient to understand the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. Probably it will be easy to recognize the presence of the archaeological remains in the context of classification. There are some technical problems to be solved according to the downloaded files.</p>		

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MAP-003 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Five classes using Validation Data (from Patricia Bay)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Demo Dataset (Bedford_2017.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Bedford 2017 for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
4. Select " Five Classes " model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 5 for this experiment)	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

<p>5. Execute the service</p>	<p>User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Mud Sand, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	<p>OK</p>	<p>Very efficient</p>
<p>6. Compare classification result with provided geological map</p>	<p>Classification map is consistent with bathymetry provided</p>	<p>OK</p>	<p>The classification results are clear and consistent with bathymetry provided</p>
<p>7. Click on “Download result” button and inspect downloaded classification map</p>	<p>The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 5 classes (labels)</p>	<p>Fail</p>	<p>There is a problem in the downloaded file there are only three colours instead of five (colour for each class). The gravel and sand with gravel classes are in black! There are obvious differences between the 4 classes and the 5 classes results in these categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mud sand with urchins - Fine mud sand - Sand with gravel <p>The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 5. The values start from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0) (The black background of the tiff file).

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (1-2) values correspond to the classified classes (Mud Sand with Urchins, Mud Sand). - (3) value is missing and it corresponds to the fine mud sand. - (4) value is in black and corresponds to the sand with gravel class. - (5) value is in black and corresponds to the gravel class. - (From 6 to 255) represent nothing?? <p style="background-color: yellow;">Check FIG.3</p>
Test result	<p>User-friendly service.</p> <p>Efficient to understand the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. Probably it will be easy to recognize the presence of the archaeological remains in the context of classification.</p> <p>There are some technical problems to be solved according to the downloaded files.</p>	

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own multispectral multibeam datasets

FIG.1. Classification with **Three classes** using **Demo Data** (from Patricia Bay), print screen from QGIS.

FIG.2. Classification with **Four classes** using **Demo Data** (from Patricia Bay), print screen from QGIS.

FIG.3. Classification with **Five classes** using **Demo Data** (from Patricia Bay), print screen from QGIS.

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U3) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-map.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Panagiotis Mertikas (NKUA) Valsamis Ntouskos (NKUA) Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA) panag.mertikas@gmail.com ntouskos@mail.ntua.gr karank@central.ntua.gr
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Jean-Christophe Sourisseau AMU
Dependencies:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ NEANIAS AAI ✓ NEANIAS DaShaS (Nextcloud) 	Date of Execution:	10/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Service access/download	https://uw-map.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service/en/latest/
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Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MAP-001 (Demo Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Three classes using Demo Data (from Newbex)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
124. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
125. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
126. Select Demo Dataset (patricia_demo.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Patricia for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI list	OK	
127. Select “ Three Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 3 for this experiment)	OK	
128. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Sand, Mud Sand, Gravel) 	OK	
129. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	The classification results are simply clear
130. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 3 classes (labels)	OK	Higher accuracy is required The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

			instead of 3. The values start from - (0) (The black background of the tiff file) - (1-2-3) values correspond to the classified classes. - (From 4 to 255) represent nothing?? Check FIG.1
Test result	User-friendly service. Efficient to understand the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed.		

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MAP-002 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Four classes using Validation Data (from Newbex)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
8. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
9. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
10. Select Demo Dataset (newbex.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Newbex for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
11. Select " Four Classes " model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 4 for this experiment)	OK	
12. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, 	OK	

Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

	Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel)		
13. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	The classification results are simply clear
14. Click on "Download result" button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 4 classes (labels)	OK	<p>Higher accuracy is required and the gravel class is black.</p> <p>The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 4. The values start from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0) (The black background of the tiff file). - (1-2-3) values correspond to the classified classes. - (4) value is in black and corresponds to the gravel class. - (From 5 to 255) are black also, but they represent nothing?? <p>Check FIG.2</p>
Test result	User-friendly service. Efficient to understand the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed.		

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MAP-003 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Five classes using Validation Data (from Newbex)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
8. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	

 Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

9. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
10. Select Demo Dataset (Bedford_2017.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Bedford 2017 for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
11. Select “ Five Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 5 for this experiment)	OK	
12. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Mud Sand, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	
13. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map is consistent with bathymetry provided	Fail	The classification results of the fine mud sand and sand with gravel are not clear. The classification map is consistent with bathymetry provided
14. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 5 classes (labels)	Fail	Higher accuracy is required. There is a problem in the downloaded file there are only three colours instead of five (colour for each class). The gravel and the sand with gravel classes are black. There are obvious differences between the

		<p>4 classes and the 5 classes results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mud sand with urchins - Sand with gravel - Gravel <p>The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 5. The values start from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0) (The black background of the tiff file). - (1-2) values correspond to the classified classes (Mud Sand with Urchins and Mud Sand). - (3) value is missing and it corresponds to the fine mud sand. - (4) value is in black and corresponds to the sand with gravel class. - (5) value is in black and corresponds to the gravel class. - (From 6 to 255) represent nothing?? <p>Check FIG.3</p>
<p>Test result</p>	<p>User-friendly service. Efficient to understand the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed.</p>	

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own multispectral multibeam datasets

FIG.1. Classification with **Three classes** using **Demo Data (from Newbex)**, print screen from QGIS.

FIG.2. Classification with **Four classes** using **Demo Data (from Newbex)**, print screen from QGIS.

FIG.3. Classification with **Five classes** using **Demo Data (from Newbex)**, print screen from QGIS.

NEANIAS UW-MAP (Underwater U3) Validation TEST LOG

<https://uw-map.neanias.eu>

Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Panagiotis Mertikas (NKUA) Valsamis Ntouskos (NKUA) Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA) panag.mertikas@gmail.com ntouskos@mail.ntua.gr karank@central.ntua.gr
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Kalliopi Baika AMU
Dependencies:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ NEANIAS AAI ✓ NEANIAS DaShaS (Nextcloud) 	Date of Execution:	10/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-map.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MAP-001 (Demo Data)
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Test Description	Classification with Three classes using Demo Data (from Bedford 2017)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
131. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
132. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
133. Select Demo Dataset (patricia_demo.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Patricia for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI list	OK	
134. Select “ Three Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 3 for this experiment)	OK	
135. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Sand, Mud Sand, Gravel) 	OK	Easy to execute. Interface of the service very user-friendly
136. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	The classification results are clear
137. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 3 classes (labels)	Fail	Higher accuracy is required. The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 3. The values start from - (0) (The black background of the tiff file)

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			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (1-2-3) values correspond to the classified classes. - (From 4 to 255) represent nothing?? <p style="background-color: yellow; display: inline-block; padding: 2px;">Check FIG.1</p>
Test result	<p>User-friendly service. Easy to use and follow the steps. The results are immediate and clear for the user to check and evaluate. Efficient service to identify the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. It seems that it will be appropriate for the recognition of archaeological features.</p>		

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MAP-002 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Four classes using Validation Data (from Bedford 2017)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
15. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
16. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
17. Select Demo Dataset (newbex.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Newbex for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
18. Select " Four Classes " model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 4 for this experiment)	OK	
19. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, 	OK	Easy to follow and user-friendly

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	Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel)		
20. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	The classification results are clear and the geological map that comes out as a result is easy to check and evaluate.
21. Click on "Download result" button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 4 classes (labels)	Fail	<p>Higher accuracy is required and the gravel class is in black.</p> <p>The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 4. The values start from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0) (The black background of the tiff file)- I deleted it. - (1-2-3) values correspond to the classified classes. - (4) value is in black and corresponds to the gravel class. - (From 5 to 255) represent nothing?? <p>Check FIG.2</p>
Test result	<p>User-friendly service. Very easy to follow the steps and have an immediate result for optical evaluation.</p> <p>Efficient service to understand the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. It seems that the service will be appropriate for the identification of the presence of the archaeological remains in the context of classification.</p>		

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MAP-003 (Validation Data)
Test Description	Classification with Five classes using Validation Data (from Bedford 2017)
Preconditions	None

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Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
15. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
16. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	Simple and clear
17. Select Demo Dataset (Bedford_2017.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Bedford 2017 for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	Easy process
18. Select “ Five Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 5 for this experiment)	OK	
19. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Mud Sand, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	Easy and simple to follow the steps. User-friendly interface
20. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map is consistent with bathymetry provided	OK	The classification results are clear and consistent with the bathymetry provided.
21. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 5 classes (labels)	Fail	There is a problem in the downloaded file - there are only four colours instead of five (colour for each class). The sand with gravel class is represented in black. There are obvious differences between the 4 classes and the 5

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			<p>classes results in the category Sand with gravel.</p> <p>The georeferenced file has a problem in classification in QGIS. There are 256 values instead of 5. The values start from</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (0) (The black background of the tiff file). - (1-2-3) values correspond to the classified classes. - (4) value is in black and corresponds to the sand with gravel class. - (5) value is in black and corresponds to the gravel class. - (From 6 to 255) represent nothing?? <p>Check FIG.3</p>
<p>Test result</p>	<p>User-friendly service. Simple and clear instructions. The steps were easy to follow.</p> <p>The service provides an immediate result for optical evaluation on every step.</p> <p>Efficient service to identify the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed.</p> <p>It seems that the service will be appropriate for the identification and study of the archaeological remains in the context of sea-bed classification.</p>		

* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own multispectral multibeam datasets

FIG.1. Classification with **Three classes** using **Demo Data** (from **Bedford 2017**), print screen from QGIS.

FIG.2. Classification with **Four classes** using **Demo Data** (from **Bedford 2017**), print screen from QGIS.

FIG.3. Classification with **Five classes** using **Demo Data** (from **Bedford 2017**), print screen from QGIS.

U3_Service Evaluation remarks by end-users (underwater archaeological community)

Testing Service U3 the overall experience is that the interface and the whole processing very user-friendly. It proved easy navigate in login page and review the documentation page, as well as to use and follow the different steps. The results are immediate and clear for the user to check. The classification results of the geological maps are easy to understand and optically evaluated by a non-experienced user. The classification results are consistent with the bathymetry provided (but this observation was not possible to be cross-checked in a QGIS environment).

However, we experienced several difficulties, when the results of all three demo databases were transferred in a QGIS environment for cross-referencing and further study and analysis (see Appendix).

- First, the georeferenced file presented problems in classification when transferred in QGIS (the values and the classes do not correspond).
- Moreover, by the comparison of the resulted classification maps, especially between the 4-classes maps and the 5-classes maps, we observed distinct differences in the categories of the classified material. For example, the zones of mud sand and

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urchins, fine mud sand and sand with gravel were attributed to different areas in the maps, when ran in the 4-classes process and in the 5-classes process, and sometimes we are losing the colour classification altogether (mostly in the 5-classes process – we are losing the blue colour and two other categories of materials both become black). Thus, in the final result, the extend of the areas cannot be accurately calculated – especially valuable in monitoring studies on marine environments (with or without archaeological features)

- Furthermore, the colours attributed to different materials did not match when processed in the 4-and 5-classes process (ex. Black colour was attributed to gravel and in the map of the 5-classes process was attributed to gravel and sand with gravel). Therefore, when the map is transferred in a QGIS environment, the different materials cannot be distinguished any more.

- Finally, higher accuracy would be expected in the produced map in a next release.

Despite the issues to be solved in the next release at least as these were observed in the optical results (no advanced knowledge on the technical aspect of the service), this is undoubtedly a very efficient service to identify the geomorphological and sedimentological features of the seabed. Therefore, it seems that this service will be appropriate and very useful for the recognition of archaeological features, though no adapted database with distinct archaeological structures was yet ran to test the U3 service, a challenge for the next release.

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Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Josep Quintana Coronis Computing
Dependencies:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ NEANIAS AAI ✓ NEANIAS DaShaS (Nextcloud) 	Date of Execution:	11/12/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-map.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MAP-001
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	(Demo Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Three classes using Demo Data (from Patricia Bay)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
138. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
139. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
140. Select Demo Dataset (patricia_demo.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Patricia for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
141. Select “ Three Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 3 for this experiment)	OK	
142. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Sand, Mud Sand, Gravel) 	OK	
143. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	Map/Bathymetry to check result is small and is not possible to resize it, it's hard to compare it
144. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 3 classes (labels)	OK	
Test result	By mistake I selected 5 classes, the software executes, but no result available		

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MAP-002 (Validation Data)
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Test Description	Classification with Four classes using Validation Data (from Newbex)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
106. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
107. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
108. Select Demo Dataset (newbex.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Newbex for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
109. Select " Four Classes " model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 4 for this experiment)	OK	
110. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	
111. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	Map/Bathymetry to check result is small and is not possible to resize it, it's hard to compare it
112. Click on " Download result " button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 4 classes (labels)	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MAP-003 (Validation Data)
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Report on the Developed and Validated Underwater Thematic Services #1

Test Description	Classification with Five classes using Validation Data (from Bedford 2017)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Demo Dataset (Bedford_2017.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Bedford 2017 for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
4. Select “ Five Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 5 for this experiment)	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Mud Sand, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	
6. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map is consistent with bathymetry provided	OK	Map/Bathymetry, I’m not able to match colours from classification result with the ones from map/bathymetry. There is no legend on it.
7. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 5 classes (labels)	OK	
Test result			

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* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own multispectral multibeam datasets

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Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Panagiotis Mertikas (NKUA) Valsamis Ntouskos (NKUA) Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA) panag.mertikas@gmail.com ntouskos@mail.ntua.gr karank@central.ntua.gr
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Danai Lampridou NKUA
Dependencies:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ NEANIAS AAI ✓ NEANIAS DaShaS (Nextcloud) 	Date of Execution:	12/11/2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-map.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MAP-001 (Demo Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Three classes using Demo Data (from Patricia Bay)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
145. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
146. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
147. Select Demo Dataset (patricia_demo.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Patricia for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI list	OK	

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148. Select “ Three Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 3 for this experiment)	OK	
149. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Sand, Mud Sand, Gravel) 	OK	
150. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	The test partially corresponds to the red box, is located NE. Muddy Sand
151. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 3 classes (labels)	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MAP-002 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Four classes using Validation Data (from Newbex)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Demo Dataset (newbex.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Newbex for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	

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4. Select “ Four Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 4 for this experiment)	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	
6. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK or Fail	The classification does not agree with the geological map.
7. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 4 classes (labels)	OK or Fail	The downloaded classification map does not have the same colors as the produced one, the class “Sand with Gravel” is missing (depicted black)
Test result			

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MAP-003 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Five classes using Validation Data (from Bedford 2017)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments

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1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Demo Dataset (Bedford_2017.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Bedford 2017 for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	
4. Select “ Five Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 5 for this experiment)	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Mud Sand, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	Bathymetry seems to be reversed (positive values), also there is no scale bar.
6. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map is consistent with bathymetry provided	OK	No geological map is provided.
7. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 5 classes (labels)	OK	The downloaded classification map does not have the same colors as the produced one, and the classes “Gravel” and “Sand with Gravel” are missing (depicted black)

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Test result	
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* *“Actual outcome”, “notes” and “test result” are compiled by the validator.*

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own multispectral multibeam datasets

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Project Name:	NEANIAS Underwater Thematic Services	Software Designed and Developed by:	Panagiotis Mertikas (NKUA) Valsamis Ntouskos (NKUA) Konstantinos Karantzas (ATHENA) panag.mertikas@gmail.com ntouskos@mail.ntua.gr karank@central.ntua.gr
Module Name:	UW-MAP	Software released date:	18/11/2020 (version 1.0.0)
Release Version:	1.0.0 (current 1.0.1)	Test Executed by:	Zafeirakopoulou Effie (NKUA)
Dependencies:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ NEANIAS AAI ✓ NEANIAS DaShaS (Nextcloud) 	Date of Execution:	12-12-2020
Test Requirements	Internet access, Modern Web Browser (e.g. IE 9+, Firefox, Edge, Chrome, Safari, Opera, etc.) OR Stock browser on Android 4.0+ and Safari on iOS 7+, Account on NEANIAS AAI OR Microsoft account OR Google account.		
Service access/download	https://uw-map.neanias.eu documentation: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/u3-service/en/latest/		

Test Case #1	TEST-UW-MAP-001 (Demo Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Three classes using Demo Data (from Patricia Bay)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
152. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
153. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
154. Select Demo Dataset (patricia_demo.tif)	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Patricia for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	

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from the Dataset list			
155. Select “ Three Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 3 for this experiment)	OK	
156. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Sand, Mud Sand, Gravel) 	OK	
157. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	
158. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 3 classes (labels)	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #2	TEST-UW-MAP-002 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Four classes using Validation Data (from Newbex)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Demo Dataset (newbex.tif) from the Dataset list	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Newbex for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI	OK	

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4. Select “ Four Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 4 for this experiment)	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	
6. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map corresponds to the classes in the test area of the geological map	OK	
7. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 4 classes (labels)	OK	
Test result			

Test Case #3	TEST-UW-MAP-003 (Validation Data)		
Test Description	Classification with Five classes using Validation Data (from Bedford 2017)		
Preconditions	None		
Test Steps	Expected Result	Actual Outcome	Notes / Comments
1. Login to the service	Service UI appears and User can select and navigate to the front page	OK	
2. Review the documentation page	User can navigate and review the documentation page	OK	
3. Select Demo Dataset (Bedford_2017.tif)	User can select of upload data. The selection (<i>Bedford 2017</i>)	OK	

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from the Dataset list	<i>for this experiment</i>) appears on the UI		
4. Select “ Five Classes ” model	User can select different targeted classes (e.g. 5 for this experiment)	OK	
5. Execute the service	User can select to execute the service. Result (previews) appear on the webpage after processing is finished. Results include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colour composite image • Classification result • Map/Bathymetry • Class sample images (Mud Sand with Urchins, Mud Sand, Fine Mud Sand, Sand with Gravel, Gravel) 	OK	
6. Compare classification result with provided geological map	Classification map is consistent with bathymetry provided	OK	
7. Click on “ Download result ” button and inspect downloaded classification map	The result is a georeferenced 1-band image with the classified 5 classes (labels)	OK	
Test result			

* “*Actual outcome*”, “*notes*” and “*test result*” are compiled by the validator.

Please add another Table for another experiment you performed with the validation data offered or your own multispectral multibeam datasets